

REGIMES OF UTLS SATELLITE-DERIVED TRENDS IN COMPOSITION (RUSTIC)**Proposal Summary**

Whereas: The upper tropospheric / lower stratospheric (UTLS) circulation is dominated by strong regional and seasonal variations that are in turn related to stratospheric polar vortex variations and to tropospheric weather regimes and extreme weather events;

Whereas: These UTLS circulation variations are manifested in tropopause and UTLS jet variations, and UTLS jet and tropopause trends have strong regional and seasonal variations;
and

Whereas: Regional variations in stratosphere-troposphere exchange (STE) and hence UTLS composition are tied to these UTLS circulation variations;

Therefore: We will evaluate the following hypotheses:

H1: *Large regional UTLS composition variations necessitate that trend evaluation must be done regionally to be robust.* That is, even the dynamical coordinate mapping used in some current studies is insufficient if done in the zonal mean, since magnitude, significance, and signs of trends will vary regionally.

H2: *Regionally resolved dynamical coordinate mapping of NASA (and other) satellite composition data will provide information to quantify regional composition trend variations.*

H3A: *Using recent high-resolution ozone and chemical reanalyses assimilating these satellite data, we can identify physically meaningful regions for quantification of UTLS composition trends.*

H3B: *High-resolution fields from these reanalyses will provide physical insight into regional variability.*

The primary satellite dataset, the 18-year+ record from the Aura Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS), will be augmented by other NASA and non-NASA satellite datasets. We will use dynamical fields and calculated diagnostics from the the most recent meteorological reanalyses from NASA (MERRA-2) and ECMWF (ERA5) to characterize dynamical processes. MERRA-2 and ERA5 assimilate MLS ozone; we will also use three chemical reanalyses (BRAM2, M2-SCREAM, TCR-2) that assimilate additional MLS measurements. We focus primarily on ozone, water vapor, and carbon monoxide, but will also examine other measured species.

Focus regions will be chosen based on significant weather / UTLS circulation patterns (e.g., monsoon circulations; cold air outbreaks (CAOs); heat waves; blocking reflected in UTLS jet and tropopause variations; regimes of North Atlantic or North Pacific jet variations). We will analyze the dynamical mechanisms driving composition differences in those regions. We will then conduct trend analyses for MLS data, using (1) linear regression and pairwise correlations; (2) multiple linear regression; and (3) dynamic linear modeling. Explanatory variables for regressions with composition data will include not only known influences such as El Niño Southern Oscillation and the Quasi-biennial Oscillation but also dynamical diagnostics we identify as relevant via the process studies described above.

Our work responds to the goals of this call by using Aura MLS data, along with other NASA and non-NASA satellite data and reanalyses, to elucidate the roles of regional dynamical processes in determining UTLS composition trends. This work will also help evaluate the adequacy of current UTLS composition measurements and assess future UTLS measurement needs.

Contents

1	Scientific, technical, and management description	1-1
1.1	Introduction	1-1
1.1.1	Objectives	1-1
1.1.2	Expected Significance	1-2
1.2	Technical approach and methodology	1-3
1.2.1	Motivation and Background	1-3
1.2.2	Composition Datasets	1-6
1.2.3	Meteorological Reanalyses	1-7
1.2.4	Chemical Reanalyses	1-7
1.2.5	Tools & Techniques	1-9
1.2.6	Trend Analysis	1-12
1.2.7	Specific Actions	1-13
1.3	Perceived Impact on State of Knowledge	1-14
1.4	Relevance to AST program objectives	1-14
1.5	Work Plan	1-15
1.5.1	Time Line for Key Tasks	1-15
1.5.2	Management Structure	1-15
2	References	2-1

1 SCIENTIFIC, TECHNICAL, AND MANAGEMENT DESCRIPTION

1.1 Introduction

1.1.1 Objectives

Quantifying variability and trends in upper tropospheric/lower stratospheric (UTLS) composition is crucial to understanding climate impacts of radiatively active substances (e.g., the largest radiative impacts from ozone and water vapor are in this region), as well as to understanding physical and biological effects of pollution transport and stratosphere-troposphere exchange (STE). UTLS composition exhibits large spatio-temporal variability at regional and sub-daily scales. The direct dynamical drivers of this variability are variations in the UTLS jets (the UT jets and the lowest reaches of the stratospheric polar vortex) and the tropopause. Jet and tropopause variability is, in turn, linked to both disturbances in the overlying stratospheric polar vortex and to extreme regional weather events in the underlying troposphere. Several current efforts aim to better quantify UTLS composition by mapping available UTLS trace gas measurements into dynamical coordinate systems (e.g., in relation to the UT jets and/or the tropopause), which facilitates segregating and analyzing together air masses influenced by different dynamical processes (e.g., tropospheric vs stratospheric, or poleward vs equatorward of the subtropical UT jet). Such efforts promise important improvements over traditional analyses of zonal means done in altitude or pressure vertical coordinates, but cannot account for different relationships of composition to the jets and tropopause engendered by regional circulations driven by a variety of physical mechanisms. We will demonstrate in the proposed project that **UTLS composition varies so much regionally that to be robust, trend evaluation must be done regionally (H1 in our hypotheses per proposal summary).**

The Aura Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS, 2004–present) provides over 18 years (so far) of daily near-global UTLS profiles of trace gases including ozone (O_3), water vapor (H_2O), carbon monoxide (CO), and many other species. Long-term records of O_3 and H_2O are also available from the Stratospheric Aerosol and Gas Experiment II (SAGE-II, 1984–2005) and SAGE III/International Space Station (SAGE-III/ISS, 2017–present), and of numerous trace gases from the Canadian Atmospheric Chemistry Experiment-Fourier Transform Spectrometer (ACE-FTS, 2004–present), albeit with much sparser sampling. Existing products allow mapping these datasets into coordinates relative to the stratospheric polar vortex, UTLS jets, and tropopause. Using MLS data, augmented by data from SAGE-II, SAGE-III/ISS, and ACE-FTS, **we will demonstrate that using regionally resolved satellite data mapped into dynamical coordinates (particularly with respect to jets and tropopause) provides the fullest available information to quantify regional variations in composition trends (H2).**

The latest meteorological reanalyses from NASA's Global Modeling and Assimilation Office (GMAO) and from the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) assimilate MLS O_3 observations. Several recent chemical reanalyses assimilate additional composition measurements from MLS and other platforms. Using the high-resolution gridded three-dimensional (3D) fields of important trace gases from these chemical reanalyses, along with corresponding meteorological fields, **will allow us to identify meaningful regions for assessment of composition variability and trends (H3A).** Studies of these chemical reanalyses will also provide physical insight into mechanisms for UTLS composition variability (H3B).

Demonstrating the above hypotheses will drive us towards our specific scientific objectives:

Objective 1: Use meteorological and composition fields from reanalyses to identify regional dynamical variations that affect composition, and to characterize the spatio-temporal scales on which and the processes by which they influence composition. (H3A, H3B).

Objective 2: From Objective 1, identify important regions to focus on for analysis of trends in dynamical coordinates, and, for each region, which dynamical coordinates are most appropriate and what dynamical processes are critical to evaluate to understand those trends. (H3A, H2).

Objective 3: From Objectives 1 and 2, use MLS and ancillary satellite data mapped in dynamical coordinate systems, in conjunction with the meteorological and chemical reanalyses, to evaluate regional trends in UTLS composition, and to relate those to trends in the dynamical processes influencing them. (H3B, H2, H1).

1.1.2 Expected Significance

Improving predictive capability for composition on both long (e.g., climate forcings) and short (e.g., STE and air quality impacts) timescales is a great challenge for Earth systems science. Our incomplete understanding of UTLS composition is a major impediment to meeting this challenge. Disagreement in UTLS O₃ among satellite datasets is thought to be due to both increasing uncertainties and difficulty of measurements in the UTLS [1–4] and to sensitivity to sampling [3, 5–7]. UTLS circulation and STE exhibit large spatio-temporal variability [e.g., 8–10], and that variability has been noted to exacerbate sensitivity to sampling [e.g., 11, 12]. Climate models often poorly represent processes controlling UTLS composition and trends therein [e.g., 7, 13–16]. For example, an unexpected continuing decrease in lowermost stratosphere (LMS) O₃ [4] was shown to be driven largely by dynamical/circulation changes [17–20]. The degree to which these LS O₃ changes are driven by anthropogenically forced versus natural variability [19, 20], as well as how these LS changes relate to changes in UT O₃, is unclear. Most comprehensive analyses of stratospheric composition trends have heretofore been focused on O₃, are often based on zonal means, and typically do not examine the UTLS in detail [3, 16, 21–23, 7, and references therein]. Uncertainties in representation of STE and mixing processes also strongly affect modeled UTLS composition and its radiative effects [e.g., 24–26].

Overarching questions regarding UTLS composition include: What are the roles of different STE mechanisms, and how will they change with climate change [27, 28]? How will changes in stratosphere-to-troposphere transport influence tropospheric composition and air quality [28, 29, e.g.]? How well can we determine past and predict future STE changes [27, 28, 30, 31]? What are the global/regional impacts of changes in UTLS composition on climate [28, 32]? More general questions regarding coupling of the UTLS to the stratospheric and tropospheric circulations include “What roles do UTLS processes play in stratosphere-troposphere coupling and extreme weather, and what are relevant coupling mechanisms?” [33]; this in turn raises the question of how stratosphere-troposphere coupling and extreme weather may affect UTLS composition.

Major UTLS circulation features such as the UT jets and tropopause show strong regional and seasonal variations in trends [e.g., 8, 34, 35] and in relationships to natural modes of variability [e.g., 36–38]. **It is thus imperative to account for spatio-temporal variability when assessing UTLS composition trends, and to understand the mechanisms driving this variability.** Equivalent latitude (EqL, defined as the latitude enclosing the same area between it and the pole as a potential vorticity, PV, contour [39]), is a useful vortex-centered coordinate in the stratosphere and has been used for some UTLS composition studies [e.g., 40–43]. But mapping in EqL cannot represent large regional variability that drives transport, or non-conservative processes in the UTLS [e.g., 44, 45].

Evaluation of UTLS composition measurements using alternative coordinate systems has been recognized as a high priority to understand and diagnose the origins of trace gas variability [3, 30], but we must go further to evaluate how regional variability in dynamical processes contributes to trace gas changes as viewed in any coordinate system.

1.2 Technical approach and methodology

1.2.1 Motivation and Background

UTLS composition variability is determined largely by relationships to UTLS jet and tropopause variations. These are in turn inextricably linked to both the overlying stratospheric circulation and chemistry and the underlying tropospheric circulation.

Interannual variability in the Arctic stratospheric winter polar vortex is very large, including weak (e.g., sudden stratospheric warmings, SSWs, such as those in early January 2013, 2019, and 2021) and strong (e.g., as in the 2010/2011 and 2019/2020 winters) vortex events and differences in the timing of the spring vortex breakdown [e.g., 46–49]. These phenomena result in large variability in the springtime lower stratospheric O₃ reservoir, which has been shown to strongly influence stratosphere-to-troposphere transport (STT) in the following months [e.g., 9, 10]. Further, extremely strong or weak states of the stratospheric polar vortex result in changes in the tropopause and UT jet streams [e.g., 26, 50]. Arctic stratospheric polar vortex variations are also linked to surface impacts [51, and references therein], including extreme weather events such as some CAOs and heat waves [e.g., 52–56]. Some CAOs have been shown to be linked more strongly to shape variations of the stratospheric vortex than to weakening [e.g., 57, 58]. The Antarctic polar vortex also influences the surface and UT jets, with the extreme annual Antarctic O₃ depletion playing a large role [e.g., 32, 59–63]. A robust poleward shift of the UT jet, with maximum changes extending east and west from southern South America, has been linked to anthropogenic forcing [e.g., 32, 59, 60, 64]. Antarctic polar vortex weakening (such as the Antarctic SSWs in 2002 and 2019) has been associated with anomalously high temperatures over Australia and equatorward shifts in UT jets [e.g., 63, 65]. Because interannual variability in the Antarctic stratospheric polar vortex becomes large only in late winter or spring [32, 47, 49, and references therein], impacts of polar vortex and polar O₃ variations on UT jets, tropopause characteristics, and STE are likely to be largest in late winter through early summer.

UT jet variations, tropopause variations, and their connections to the stratospheric vortex as described above are associated with regional variability in the tropospheric circulation, and thus such variability is expected to influence STE: CAOs are associated with large excursions and blocking of the UT jet streams [e.g., 66–71]. Some of the earliest papers on tropopause folds (which transport stratospheric air into the troposphere) showed them to be associated with upper-level frontal systems [e.g., 72–74]. Mesoscale systems such as “tropopause polar cyclones” (TPCs) are characterized by a deep depression in tropopause altitude, which results in closed isentropes on the dynamical tropopause, and with anomalously cold air below that lowered tropopause [e.g., 75–78] (TPCs are referred to as “tropopause polar vortices” in some literature; we choose an alternate term mentioned by [76] to avoid confusion of these mesoscale days-to-weeks-long events, which often move out of polar latitudes [e.g., 78], with the stratospheric polar vortex [per 79]). Recent studies have linked TPCs to many CAOs [e.g., 77, 80, 78]. The extreme tropopause depressions in TPCs [wherein the tropopause altitude may dip near the surface, below 850 hPa; e.g., 78] are expected to bring stratospheric air deep into the troposphere, and thus to strongly affect local UTLS trace gas distributions; they have previously been related to STE [e.g., 81]. Large excursions of the UT jets are directly linked to blocking (typically defined by some direct or indirect measure of the jet being “blocked” from its climatological path) [e.g., 69, 70, 82, 83], and thus in turn to

CAOs [e.g., 68, 84]. Recent work has explored STE associated with CAOs, for example [85] showed evidence of stratosphere-to-troposphere transport associated with tropopause folding during the February 2021 CAO over the US Great Plains.

Monsoon circulations are important phenomena spanning tropospheric through lower stratospheric altitudes and tropical to mid-latitude air mass characteristics; they have a profound influence on summertime UTLS and lower stratospheric composition [e.g., 86–90]. The Asian summer monsoon (ASM) circulation has been most studied and overall has the largest impacts, but UTLS trace gas variations are also associated with the North American summer monsoon (NASM), the Australian summer monsoon (AuSM), and the South American summer monsoon (SAmSM) [e.g., 91–95]. Previous work has shown transport between the tropical UT and extratropical LS (in both directions) associated with eddy-shedding and Rossby wave breaking (RWB) related to monsoon anticyclones [e.g., 89, 92, 96–99]. The monsoon circulations are bounded on the poleward side by the subtropical jet [which shifts poleward around those circulations during summer, e.g., 100, 101, and references therein] and on the equatorward side by the tropical easterly jet, as well as being associated with regional displacements of the tropopause [e.g., 102–104].

RWB is a key mechanism for mixing and transport in the vicinity of the UTLS jets, tropopauses, monsoon anticyclones, and stratospheric polar vortex [e.g., 105, 96, 106, 107, 97, 98, 108]. It also drives and responds to changes in the UT jets and the stratospheric vortex [e.g., 109–115]. RWB is commonly associated with multiple lapse rate tropopauses (LRTs) and accompanying tropospheric intrusions into the stratosphere [e.g., 106], and has been linked to weather regime transitions [e.g., 116].

Given these links of UTLS dynamics and composition to both the stratospheric circulation above and the tropospheric circulation below, we want to analyze the composition data referenced to a wide variety of metrics, to represent variability in UTLS, stratospheric, and tropospheric circulations that influences UTLS composition changes. Because of the different dominant scales of motion and dynamical mechanisms in the stratosphere and troposphere, multiple diagnostics are needed to best characterize different regions, as discussed below.

The stratospheric polar vortex is a single approximately circumpolar feature that dominates the hemispheric circulation during winter (Fig. 1a), with winds sharply peaked along the edge of that circulation (Fig. 1b), and strong trace gas gradients and nearly constant trace gas mixing ratios along the vortex edge (Fig. 1c,d). This is why the stratospheric circulation and composition variability can readily be evaluated in hemispheric means (often in zonal means, or, where that is

Figure 2: (Center) 345 K MERRA-2 O₃ on 6 January 2014 in the NH and 4 September 2019 in the SH. Overlays are wind speeds (black, from 30 m/s by 10 m/s), the 2 PVU tropopause (dark red), and STJ core latitudes (white dots). (Left) zonal mean O₃ (dark/light green) and wind speed (black/grey) from the central map. (Right) O₃ and wind speed averaged with latitude relative to the STJ as the y-coordinate. Shading on line plots is the 1- σ envelope.

inadequate, in EqL coordinates that map trace gas distributions with respect to the polar vortex) [7, 117–119, and references therein].

In contrast, the UT circulation is characterized by a complex system of jet streams and tropopause variations with strong regional variations (e.g., Fig. 1a), leading to broad distributions of windspeeds and widely varying trace gas abundances and gradients (Fig. 1b,c,d). [See, e.g., 79, for further discussion of contrasting stratospheric and tropospheric circulations]. Thus, in the UTLS large regional variability makes using zonal means — and even longitudinally averaged referencing to a dynamical coordinate — problematic. As expected, zonal means (Fig. 2, left) wash out strong windspeed maxima and strong O₃ gradients. It has been further shown that EqL (a very effective geophysical coordinate in the stratosphere) is often not helpful in the UTLS [44, 45]. This realization, and studies effectively using tropopause-relative vertical coordinates [40, 120–122, and references therein], motivated the use of jet stream locations as horizontal and/or vertical coordinates [e.g., 44, 123], as well as the use of latitudinal tropopause-relative coordinates [e.g., 124, 125]. Figure 2 (right) exemplifies using a jet-relative latitude coordinate for UTLS O₃ — wind speed maxima and strong O₃ gradients are, indeed, somewhat better represented near the jet core (but only within 5–10° of it) and variability in the wind speeds is much reduced in that region. Subtropical jet locations tend to follow the dynamical tropopause (overlaid on the O₃ maps in Fig. 2); coordinates based on jet and/or tropopause locations thus do highlight STE. However, O₃ variability remains quite large in the jet-relative coordinate view, as expected from the appearance of the maps in Figs. 2 and 1c. In the Northern Hemisphere (NH) winter, multiple tropopauses and RWB are both common near 150° to 120°W and 45°W to 0° [e.g., 96, 126, 105], and weaker and wavier jets associated with those are consistent with the weaker O₃ gradients in these regions (Fig. 2). In the example for 6 January 2014, the double-jet region over the eastern Pacific and western North America accompanies the blocking ridge associated with the January 2014 CAO [e.g. 127, 128], and also bounds a large region of relatively low O₃ and weak O₃ gradients. While the Southern Hemisphere (SH) UT circulation is somewhat more symmetric, it is still dominated by strong regional variations in the UT jets and tropopauses [e.g., 126], and the SH map in Fig. 2 again shows very strong variations in O₃ and O₃ gradients and windspeeds along the tropopauses.

Given these strong regional variations, for the most robust characterization of equivalent air masses, we must go further and focus separately on regions with different relationships to the jets and tropopauses.

Figure 3 shows examples of some potential longitude regions that might be used for examining the influence of different processes on trace gas distributions. A variety of influences in different regions is suggested by the climatology and by previous work, including:

Figure 3: Climatological jet frequency distributions during the solstice seasons, with examples of longitude regions of high natural variability related to different dynamical processes. Legends note some of the circulation variations that impact transport and stratosphere-troposphere exchange in each region, for (left) DJF and (right) JJA.

- Highly variable multiple jets (with the polar jet often dominant) over the Northeast Pacific and North Atlantic, associated with regions of enhanced RWB and STE [e.g., 10, 96] and with North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) variations that impact European extreme weather events [e.g., 129–131].
- Strong near-zonal NH subtropical jet over Africa and Asia, especially in winter. Strong near-zonal SH subtropical jet extending from the Southern Indian Ocean west to the central Pacific in June–July–August (JJA) [e.g., 8, 132, 126, 133].
- Northward tilting subtropical jet extending from the North Pacific over western North America in both seasons, associated with extensions / retractions of the North Pacific (polar) jet and STE variations [e.g., 10, 134, 135].
- ASM and NASM circulations in JJA; AuSM and SAmSM circulations in December–January–February (DJF) [e.g., 91, 101].
- Tropical westerly jet over the southeastern Pacific in DJF, associated with the Walker circulation during the AuSM and with “westerly ducts” [e.g., 126, 136–138].

1.2.2 Composition Datasets

The satellite composition datasets used here are from ongoing missions that are well-validated and documented. The current versions of these datasets are described briefly below; as new versions become available during the project we will transition to using those following recommendations from the instruments’ science teams. All of these satellite datasets have been extensively validated, including multi-sensor comparisons of O_3 and H_2O to ground-based observations and intercomparisons among satellite instruments [e.g., 2, 12, 139].

Aura Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS): The Aura MLS [140] version 5 (v5) dataset is a powerful tool for studying UTLS composition, providing an unparalleled combination of a long record (2004–present) of vertically resolved (3–4 km in the UTLS) composition data with near-global daily coverage (~ 3500 profiles/day from $\sim 82^\circ S$ to $82^\circ N$) and high-quality UTLS measurements [141]. Numerous studies of UTLS composition use MLS observations [e.g., 44, 87, 93, 125, 142–147]; many of these studies use some of the dynamical diagnostics described below (Section 1.2.5).

SAGE II & SAGE III/ISS Datasets: SAGE II (1984–2005, v7) [148, 149] and SAGE-III/ISS (2017–present, currently v5.2) [150–152] provide solar occultation measurements (~ 30 profiles/day) at 0.5–1.0 km vertical resolution; their sampling focuses on low to mid-latitudes and thus is well-suited for UT studies related to the influence of subtropical to mid-latitude processes (such as jet and tropopause variations, monsoon circulations, etc.) on composition. [153] used V7 SAGE II data in a tropopause-relative climatology of O_3 profiles. [151] reported a UTLS bias in SAGE III/ISS O_3 that has been corrected in v5.2. SAGE III/ISS H_2O climatological and seasonal variations agree well with those seen by MLS, including high values in the ASM and NASM regions [154].

SAGE II and SAGE III/ISS O₃ data, along with Optical Spectrograph and InfraRed Imaging System (OSIRIS) data, were used in a recent study of stratospheric O₃ trends, which showed that lower stratospheric trends were strongly influenced by tropopause variability [155].

ACE-FTS: The ACE-FTS dataset (2004–present, v4) provides ~30 profiles/day with effective UTLS resolution near 1 km [156], focused largely on the polar regions. Several studies using ACE-FTS data focus on the UTLS: [122] use ACE-FTS data in a comprehensive study of the extra-tropical tropopause layer, [157] provide a monthly climatology of ACE-FTS data as a function of EqL covering the UTLS, and [158] compare climatological O₃ and H₂O from ACE-FTS with two other Canadian satellite datasets and a specified-dynamics chemistry climate model (CCM).

1.2.3 Meteorological Reanalyses

The primary operational reanalyses to be used here are MERRA-2 [159] and ERA5 [160], both of which assimilate MLS O₃ [for details of O₃ assimilation in numerous reanalyses, see 161]. Existing dynamical diagnostics (described below along with others that are under development), both on the reanalysis grids and interpolated to MLS measurement locations, are available from these reanalyses [personal communication]. These will be used in analysis of dynamical influences and evaluation of assimilated trace gases. MERRA-2 will be used initially for mapping satellite data into dynamical coordinates, with comparisons added using ERA5. The reanalyses differ in data assimilation methods, input datasets, and resolution and placement of model levels [e.g., 161, 162, see their Figure 2.1 for vertical grids]. The reanalyses will be used on (or near for spectral models) their native model grid, with ~0.5° (~0.3°) horizontal resolution and ~1 km (~0.3) vertical resolution for MERRA-2 (ERA5). Even recent high-resolution reanalyses such as these show differences in their representation of the tropopauses, UTLS jets, and the trends therein [e.g., 163, 8, 35, 164]; in aspects of ASMA variability and trends [e.g., 101, 165]; and in variability and distributions of assimilated O₃ and H₂O [e.g., 147, 161]. [161] show broad climatological agreement in O₃ fields from recent operational reanalyses, with (as expected since they assimilate MLS observations in a consistent manner) best representations in MERRA-2 and ERA5. In contrast, assimilation of UTLS and stratospheric H₂O in even recent reanalyses is limited (e.g., some do not assimilate H₂O above the tropopause), and that is reflected in poor representation of stratospheric H₂O [161].

1.2.4 Chemical Reanalyses

In addition to the satellite data and meteorological reanalyses, this project will use three chemical reanalyses that span and focus on the Aura mission period, each of which assimilates v4 MLS data for several species. The chemical reanalyses provide high-resolution 3D global gridded datasets at sub-daily intervals that are closely constrained by composition data, at least partly from MLS. The reanalyses vary in their vertical domains, vertical and horizontal resolution, assimilation methods, chemical models, which MLS species are assimilated, and whether (and if so which) composition observations from other platforms are assimilated. Each has some advantages and disadvantages for UTLS studies; for example, BRAM2 assimilates the most MLS species that are potentially useful in the UTLS (e.g., it is the only one that assimilates MLS CO), M2-SCREAM has the best horizontal resolution in the UTLS, while TCR-2 better represents tropospheric chemistry and emissions. They thus provide a range of fields for intercomparison and for evaluating the robustness of their representations of UTLS spatio-temporal composition variability.

BRAM2: The Belgian Assimilation System for Chemical Observations (BASCOE) Reanalysis of Aura MLS, version 2 (BRAM2) reanalysis assimilates MLS observations using an ensemble Kalman filter (EnKF) method and a chemical transport model driven by the winds and temperature from ERA-Interim [166]. The model resolution is 3.75° × 2.5° latitude-longitude grid, with 37 vertical levels from the surface to 0.1 hPa, 25 of those above 100 hPa, providing about 1–1.5 km vertical

Figure 4: Examples of M2-SCREAM H₂O (left) and HCl (right) fields at 345 K for the dates / hemispheres shown in Fig. 2, showing a high-resolution view of large regional variations in trace gases and evidence of quasi-isentropic STE.

resolution in the UTLS. Six-hourly fields are available. BRAM2 assimilates MLS O₃, H₂O, N₂O, HNO₃, HCl, ClO, CH₃Cl, and CO; fields extending into the UTLS of O₃, H₂O, HNO₃, CO, and CH₃Cl are provided, and all of these will be included in some evaluations, though we focus mostly on O₃, H₂O, and CO. [166] evaluated O₃, H₂O, CO, and CH₃Cl in the UTLS. Their results suggested a high (low) bias of MLS O₃ (H₂O) in the upper troposphere, but generally good agreement of O₃ with independent sonde measurements. All four of these BRAM2 products are recommended for scientific use in the UTLS, with some limitations.

M2-SCREAM: The MERRA-2 Stratospheric Composition Reanalysis of Aura Microwave Limb Sounder (M2-SCREAM) [167] is described in detail by [168, submitted to ESSD]. This reanalysis assimilates version 4.2 [169] MLS H₂O, N₂O, HCl, HNO₃, and O₃ profiles using a constituent data assimilation system endowed with a full stratospheric chemistry module and driven by assimilated meteorological fields from MERRA-2. An earlier version of this assimilated product was used in a study of the 2019 Antarctic ozone hole [118]. As shown by [168], the assimilated species are in excellent agreement with MLS observations and realistically capture the spatial and temporal variability of these species; good agreement is also seen with independent observations from ACE-FTS (where differences mainly reflect known biases between MLS and ACE-FTS data) and in the representation of fine-scale structure near the tropopause in comparison with aircraft measurements. M2-SCREAM products are provided eight times per day on the same grid as MERRA-2, with 72 hybrid σ -pressure levels from the surface to 0.01 hPa (~1 km vertical resolution in the UTLS), and a $0.625^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ longitude-latitude grid. N₂O is not assimilated below ~68 hPa (the lowest level the v4 MLS N₂O data were recommended for scientific use); thus near/below tropopause level, those fields are primarily determined by the modeled transport. Examples of SCREAM H₂O and HCl fields near the tropopause are shown in Fig. 4.

TCR-2: The Tropospheric Chemistry Reanalysis version 2 (TCR-2) [170] is a state-of-the-art multi-constituent chemical reanalysis for 2005–present produced using a data assimilation system based on an EnKF [171] that simultaneously optimizes chemical concentrations and emission sources. TCR-2 includes a detailed representation of tropospheric and stratospheric chemistry coupled to an atmospheric general circulation model that is nudged towards 6-hourly ERA-Interim reanalyses [172, 173]; TCR-2 will be continued beyond 2019 using ERA5 meteorological fields. The model has T106 spectral resolution (about $1.1^\circ \times 1.1^\circ$); the data are provided on 27 pressure levels from 1000–60 hPa, with about 1–1.5 km spacing in the UTLS. Numerous species from different sensors are assimilated, including (most directly relevant here) O₃ and HNO₃ from MLS and total column CO from Measurements of Pollution In The Troposphere. Comparisons against independent satellite, airborne, and ground-based measurements show that observed seasonal and interannual

variations are reproduced well on both regional and global scales from the lower troposphere to the lower stratosphere [171–174]. TCR-2 has proven valuable for validating CCMs and evaluating the representativeness of ground-based and airborne observations [173, 174]. TCR-2 provides O₃ fields produced with and without assimilating Aura Tropospheric Emission Spectrometer (TES) data through 2010; the dataset without TES assimilation provides a more consistent record for trend evaluation [173]. TCR-2 six-hourly fields for O₃, CO, and HNO₃ will be used herein.

1.2.5 Tools & Techniques

Most of the tools / derived products to be used in the RUSTIC analysis are already available or are being developed for currently funded projects. The main tools to be used are summarized below.

UTLS Jet and Tropopause Diagnostics: Numerous methods have been used to characterize upper tropospheric jets and tropopauses [e.g., 8, 35, 44, 132, 175–178]. Here we identify upper tropospheric jets as windspeed maxima greater than 40 ms⁻¹ [44]; “subtropical” jets are distinguished from “polar” jets in a physically meaningful way by requiring a sufficient drop in tropopause height from the poleward to the equatorward side of the jet [8]. Lapse rate tropopauses (LRTs) are identified using the World Meteorological Organization criteria, and multiple LRTs as in [175] and [44]. The “subvortex” jet (the lowest reaches of the polar night jet that bounds the stratospheric polar vortex edge, extending into the lowermost stratosphere) is identified as a function of height as the most poleward westerly windspeed maximum at each level (with additional conditions to identify the jet bounding each offspring vortex during vortex splits) [e.g., 44]. The bottom of the subvortex jet can merge with the top of a UT jet, indicating direct interactions [e.g., 126]. Jet and tropopause characteristics calculated from MERRA-2 and ERA5 are available on the reanalysis grids noted above (as well as the same diagnostics from several other recent reanalyses including the Japan Meteorological Agency’s JRA-55) [personal communication]. Meteorological fields available at the UT and subvortex jet locations include zonal and meridional winds, temperature, vertical temperature gradient (dT/dz), PV, relative vorticity, and vertical distance from the tropopauses. Tropopause characteristics (for both primary and all higher instances) include altitude, pressure, temperature, potential temperature, lapse rate (for dynamical tropopauses), and PV (for LRT tropopauses).

Stratospheric Polar Vortex Diagnostics: Strong and weak stratospheric polar vortices are most commonly identified using the Northern or Southern Annular Mode Indices (NAM or SAM), which are calculated using polar cap averaged fields or the leading EOF mode of the geopotential height field [179, 52, 32, 54, and references therein]. These calculations can depend strongly not only on the strength of the polar vortex, but also on its geometry and position [180]. To diagnose the polar vortex state in a way that more clearly distinguishes between effects of the intensity and geometry of the stratospheric polar vortex, we use results from software for calculating moments and related diagnostics [e.g., 181, 182] that included identification of multiple vortices and diagnostics of vortex-edge averaged windspeed and PV gradients [183]. These diagnostics are available for the NH [personal communication] and will continue to be updated for MERRA-2 and JRA-55. Similar diagnostics will be calculated using existing software for ERA5 and for each reanalysis for the SH.

Figure 5 shows examples of strong regional variations (which are expected to drive composition differences) in the relationships between some of the UTLS jet and stratospheric polar vortex diagnostics used here. For example, stronger and higher UT jets and much more frequent merged subvortex and UT jets are seen over the North Atlantic for stronger stratospheric vortices (as determined using vortex-edge averaged windspeed), and merging of the subvortex jet with the subtropical UT jet is seen over east Asia and the western Pacific for weak vortices.

Figure 5: Examples of regional relationships between lower stratospheric (520 K) polar vortex strength and UTLS jet diagnostics: (Left) Composites of occurrence frequency of merged subvortex and upper tropospheric jets (colorfill) and UT jet windspeed (black contours, 56 to 74 by 8 m s^{-1} during January-February-March (JFM) under weak and strong vortex conditions determined by 10th/90th percentile anomalies from climatology of 520 K vortex-edge averaged windspeeds. (Right) Slopes of linear regression of UT polar jet altitude and windspeed versus 520 K vortex-edge averaged windspeed (from MERRA-2 and JRA-55 reanalyses, with larger magnitude slope in transparent colors; whiskers show larger of standard errors of regressions; cases where the correlation is significant at the 95% confidence level are shown in color, others in grey).

UTLS Dynamical Diagnostics at Satellite Measurement Locations: Numerous dynamical diagnostics interpolated and/or calculated from MERRA-2 are publicly available at the MLS, ACE-FTS, and SAGE II and SAGE III/ISS measurement locations [44, 184, 185]. These include the meteorological fields provided in the reanalyses interpolated to the measurement locations, plus relative vorticity, horizontal PV and temperature gradients, dT/dz , static stability, and Montgomery streamfunction (MSF). These fields are also available on latitude / height slices at the longitudes of the measurements to characterize the surrounding environment [44]. The jet and tropopause characteristics described above are also available at MLS locations for JRA-55 and ERA5 [personal communication]. These diagnostics have been used in numerous studies for, e.g., distinguishing tropospheric and stratospheric air and for mapping stratospheric and UTLS trace gas fields into dynamical coordinates (typically with respect to jets, tropopauses, and/or equivalent latitude) [e.g., 44, 93, 123, 147, 157, 158, 186–188].

Monsoon Diagnostics: Since the monsoon circulations are bounded on the poleward side by the subtropical jet and on the equatorward side by the tropical easterly jet and are also associated with local displacements of the tropopause [e.g., 101, 126, 103, 104], the jet and tropopause diagnostics described above are useful in evaluating monsoon-related trace gas variations. In addition, we use contours of Montgomery streamfunction (MSF) to identify monsoon anticyclone boundaries and characterize the composition within and around them [e.g., 87], as well as moments diagnostics [182, 183, and references therein] to characterize their geometry and examine variability and trends therein [101]. These diagnostics have been calculated for the ASM anticyclone from each of the meteorological reanalyses used herein and will continue to be updated [personal communication]; the same methods can be used to characterize the NASM, SAmSM, and AuSM anticyclones.

Mixing and STE Diagnostics: Negative latitudinal PV gradients (calculated as part of existing diagnostics described above provide a basic measure of RWB regions [e.g., 110]; more comprehensive methods identify cyclonic versus anticyclonic RWB [e.g., 96, 105, 112]. Similar to [105], cyclonic and anticyclonic RWB regions will be identified on isentropic surfaces throughout the UTLS along a range of PV contours covering the regions of strong PV gradients representing the tropopause at

each UTLS level and the stratospheric polar (sub)vortex edge at levels in the lowermost and lower stratosphere. These RWB diagnostics are already being developed for use in a current project. Examination of PV gradients themselves (and their relationships to trace gas gradients) also provides a geographically resolved picture of regions with stronger or weaker mixing. Multiple dynamical tropopauses (which are among the UTLS jet and tropopause diagnostics described above) provide a measure of tropopause folding (and hence stratospheric intrusions), whereas multiple LRTs are often associated with RWB and tropospheric intrusions [e.g., 106].

Diagnostics of Regional Tropospheric Circulation Features: As discussed above, many tropospheric weather and climate extremes are coupled to tropopause and UT jet variations, as well as often having links to the stratospheric polar vortices [e.g., 50, 57, 78, 128]. Different tropospheric circulation patterns are expected to be associated with distinct patterns of and changes in composition. Assessing the degree to which regional tropospheric circulation features are linked to distinct signatures in UTLS composition will be valuable for identifying spatio-temporal regions, or indeed tropospheric regimes not defined by geography, that may be used to define “condition-space” regions, for assessment of composition variability and trends. Such features may include blocking, CAOs, and TPCs.

Blocking: Numerous methods are used to derive blocking indices [see review material in, e.g., 82, 83, 189]. Most of these are based on identifying either contour folding (reversed gradients) or absolute anomalies, or a combination of the two, in 500 hPa geopotential heights or in potential temperature on the 2 PVU surface. The method to be used herein is similar to that of [189, 190], whereby we identify blocking at latitudes in a relatively broad band for each longitude and apply additional criteria for spatial and temporal proximity to link individual identifications to coherent blocking events.

Cold Air Outbreaks: CAOs and other extreme temperature events are typically identified by anomalies in surface or near-surface temperatures [134, 191, and references therein], either as anomalies from climatology [e.g., 78, 192] or as the tails of observed distributions fit to appropriate functions based on extreme value theory [e.g., 134, 191, 193, 194]. We will identify CAO regions based on departures from climatology and thresholds for persistence, then describe the geometry of those regions by using computer vision methods [similar to, e.g., 183], which will provide diagnostics of the extent, centroid location, and shape of the regions.

Tropopause Polar Cyclones: Because of the associated deep depression of the tropopause, TPCs can be identified by closed potential temperature contours on the dynamical tropopause [e.g., 76], and TPC tracking algorithms are publicly available [195].

Weather Regimes and Pattern Analysis: Another way to identify composition variations with persistent or recurrent circulation features in the troposphere is by examining composition patterns associated with “weather regimes” [e.g., 130, 196, 128, 197, 198]. If UTLS composition shows distinct patterns during different weather regimes, then such regimes could be used as a “condition-space region” for assessing trends (in appropriate dynamical coordinates). Weather regimes are commonly identified using a clustering analysis done on an appropriate number of principal components from an empirical orthogonal function analysis, as described in more detail by [199, 197]. We will use similar methods to identify weather regimes, not only over North America, the North Atlantic, and Eurasia [as in, e.g., 116, 128, 134, 198, 200], but also in regions of the SH [as in, e.g. 201–204]. For the latter we will focus on Antarctic late winter through early summer – the period when the stratospheric polar vortex is becoming most depleted in O₃ and then breaking up, leading to stronger impacts of the stratosphere on the tropopause and tropospheric circulation, as well as both radiative and STE-related downward impacts of stratospheric O₃ depletion throughout

Figure 6: Examples of O₃ trends from MERRA-2, JRA-55 and ERA5 reanalyses inside the ASM anticyclone and in the ASM region but outside the anticyclone, at 350 K (mostly in troposphere) and 390 K (in LMS). (Left) Time series of O₃ mixing ratios (ppbv) over 1979–2020 for JJA; (right) slopes of linear trends (ppbv / year), with trends deemed to be significant at the 95% confidence level shown in color and others in grey.

the troposphere [32, and references therein]. 500 hPa GPH fields are used in many studies [e.g., 128, 197, 198, 202, 205] and will be used here.

1.2.6 Trend Analysis

While our ultimate goal is to improve assessment and interpretation of UTLS composition trends, our focus is on doing so primarily through identifying the most appropriate regions (and for each of those the most appropriate dynamical or “condition-space” coordinates based on the dominating processes) for trend analysis. We therefore approach the trend analysis itself not by investigating newer or extended methods for trend evaluation, but rather by using a hierarchy of well-validated and documented tools. We will thus quantify composition trends and time series covariability between composition and dynamical diagnostics using three methods:

Linear regression and pairwise correlation: These methods are very simple, intuitive, and widely used; such correlations make readily apparent the observed relationships between individual pairs of variables. Relevant to our studies, for example, are studies of relationships of tropospheric O₃ variability and trends to stratospheric O₃, QBO, and ENSO [29]; trends in UT jet streams [206] including regional and seasonal differences [8, 207]; trends in ASM anticyclone area and moments diagnostics [101] (also see Fig. 6 for an example of linear trend calculations for reanalysis O₃ in the ASM region); studies of regional and seasonal variability in UT jets linked to ENSO and other modes of variability [37, 38]; and trends in tropospheric circulation (winds and temperatures) in ERA5 [133]. For our studies, statistical significance will be assessed using bootstrapping (for correlation analysis) [e.g., 208] or permutation (for trends) [e.g., 209] analysis [e.g., 8, 29, 38, 101]. This simple trend and correlation analysis will also be used in an exploratory way to help identify which dynamical diagnostics are more appropriate to use as explanatory variables in the more complex trend analyses described below.

Multiple Linear Regression (MLR): MLR has been used in numerous trend and correlation studies to diagnose the contributions of multiple explanatory variables to variability in a field and diagnose trends in the “residual” that is not explained by those variables. Relevant examples include studies of trends and variability in stratospheric O₃ [e.g., 32, 155, 210–212] and in O₃ mapped in coordinates with respect to the subtropical UT jet [123]. Numerous standard packages are publicly available for MLR, for examples, the LOTUS regression model [7] facilitates piecewise linear regression.

Dynamical Linear Model (DLM) Regression: DLM packages, such as the publicly available one developed by [213], have recently been widely used for analysis of stratospheric O₃ trends [e.g., 4, 19, 155, 211, 214]. The DLM method includes a smooth non-linear trend component that allows it to resolve more complex behavior in long-term changes and drivers thereof than the linear or

piecewise linear methods described above [e.g., 19, 214].

Robustness of trends: Commonly used statistical tests, such as those mentioned above, do not in themselves provide an indicator of robust trends (or hence the lack thereof). Previous work has shown that different reanalyses may show highly statistically significant trends in opposite directions for some regional and seasonal diagnostics [e.g., 8]; thus it is important to confirm trends by using multiple reanalyses and/or datasets. Further, trends in geophysical fields that are small enough to be deemed insignificant may in fact be real if they are part of regional patterns that have opposite trends consistent with the driving physical processes, or other situations with strong gradients in the geophysical fields [e.g., 133]. Recent work has highlighted the importance of physical reasoning and prior knowledge in assessment of trends in geophysical fields [e.g., 215]. Thus, while statistical tests such as those mentioned above can provide a useful guide in identifying robust trends, assessment and interpretation of trends must also rely on consistency among datasets and analysis methods and on knowledge of geophysical processes. Analyzing trends in spatio-temporal or condition-space regions based on the dominant physical mechanisms in those regions builds awareness of those processes into our analysis.

1.2.7 Specific Actions

The above methods and diagnostics (most of which are already implemented or in the process of being implemented for current projects) give us a comprehensive toolkit to accomplish our stated objectives. The MLS dataset already provides over 18 years of high-quality daily near-global trace gas observations (with ACE-FTS and SAGE II & SAGE III/ISS providing comparably long or longer, though much sparser, records), thus our objectives can readily be achieved even if some of these measurements are terminated. Specific actions to achieve our objectives are as follows:

For Objective 1: We will assess regional trace gas climatology and variability (starting with O₃, H₂O, and CO) from chemical reanalyses. We will relate that to climatology and variability of the UTLS jets, tropopause (including multiple LRTs and tropopause folds) by doing field correlations and time series correlations in narrow (e.g., 20°) longitude bands. Based on relationships (being derived for current projects, e.g., Fig. 5) between UTLS jet and tropopause variability and that of the stratospheric vortices, surface conditions, and natural modes of variability such as ENSO, QBO, and NAO, we will evaluate trace gas variability in regions where UTLS jet and tropopause characteristics depend on (1) stratospheric polar vortex variations, and (2) extreme weather events, especially TPCs and CAOs. We will assess the relationships of the links indicated by these studies to RWB and blocking to help understand the dynamical mechanisms. Finally, we will construct trace gas composites in broader regions during different weather regimes (e.g., North American [e.g., 128, 198]), North Atlantic/European [e.g., 131, 200], and in several regions of the SH [e.g., 202, 204]). We will also assess the impact of time resolution on identification and characterization of dynamical / composition linkages by assessing how well time averages, up to and including monthly means, of the reanalysis data represent these relationships. **Objective 1** will primarily use the reanalyses trace gas fields to take advantage of their high-resolution global fields and dynamical diagnostics for these process-focused studies.

For Objective 2: We will use the results of **Objective 1** to select a set of condition-space regions (both geographic regions and weather regimes) for comprehensive trend analysis. The results of **Objective 1** will also facilitate selecting the dynamical diagnostics that are most critical to include as explanatory variables for the MLR and DLM analysis. Those results will further allow us to select and test the most appropriate dynamical coordinates to use for each condition-space region. Trends derived from simple linear regression can be used extensively in such testing. For this

testing, we will also compare trends derived from MLS data with those derived from the chemical reanalyses to help us understand how the assimilation processes may affect the evaluation of trends.

For Objective 3: We will set up and run trend analyses based on the conclusions from **Objectives 1 and 2**. For these studies we will also evaluate trends in MLS-measured species that are not assimilated in the chemical reanalyses to help understand their role in regional composition variations. We will also derive trends from the SAGE and ACE-FTS datasets (including additional species from ACE-FTS) and assess the extent to which the combination of regional and dynamical-coordinate selection, and/or the use of time means (assessed as part of **Objective 1**) to improve coverage, mitigates issues related to the sparse sampling of these datasets. SAGE trends will initially be calculated for the ~20-year SAGE II record, and eventually joined with the SAGE III record after assessment of biases between the two. Composition trends will be analyzed in the context of trends in the dominant dynamical processes in each region.

1.3 Perceived Impact on State of Knowledge

Improved understanding of UTLS composition variability, and how it is changing with the climate, is a critical research priority. Because of the recognition that methods that are effective for assessing stratospheric variability are inadequate to represent UTLS processes (e.g., the SPARC Data Initiative noted the need for “*A detailed UTLS measurement intercomparison, using...diagnostic tools that minimise geophysical variability and differences in vertical resolution*” [3]). While some efforts, such as those of the SPARC OCTAV-UTLS activity [216–218], are beginning to assess UTLS composition trends and variability in appropriate dynamical coordinate systems, the work for this project will go beyond that in not only **robustly quantifying the observed regional and seasonal differences in UTLS composition trends**, but also in **providing physical insight into the processes driving those trends by linking them to dynamical mechanisms controlling regional circulation features**. These studies will be **highly valuable in evaluating the adequacy of current UTLS composition measurements and assessing future UTLS measurement needs**. These studies will also address goals formulated at the SPARC UTLS Workshop in 2018, including “*Can we better quantify trends and variability and their driving processes in the UTLS?*”, “*Which feedback mechanisms on multiple scales affect large scale circulation and climate?*”, and (particularly) “*What roles do UTLS processes play for stratosphere-troposphere coupling and extreme weather, and what are relevant coupling mechanisms?*”.

This work will also **guide future evaluation of the representation of UTLS regional variability and trends in CCMs, thus improving our ability to predict UTLS composition changes under different climate change scenarios**. Applying the methods developed and used herein to chemistry-climate model (CCM) evaluation will provide added value in assessing those model datasets and their representation of the key relationships between dynamics and composition, thus improving confidence in future model projections. Since most model intercomparison projects prioritize archiving the simulations comprehensively (including the model-resolution 3D fields needed for the type of analyses in this project) only as monthly mean fields [e.g., 219–221], our assessment how well monthly means capture those relationships in reanalyses will be valuable for CCM assessment.

1.4 Relevance to AST program objectives

The work in this proposal is directed at the Atmospheric Composition Focus Area science questions of “*How is atmospheric composition changing?*” and “*How does atmospheric composition respond to and affect global environmental change?*” In particular it responds to the Aura Science Team goal of

Figure 7: Project timeline.

“Using Aura data to better understand processes and track changes in stratospheric and tropospheric composition, determine the exchange of trace gases ... between the stratosphere and troposphere, and estimate the transport properties of the stratosphere and upper troposphere”.

1.5 Work Plan

1.5.1 Time Line for Key Tasks

Figure 7 shows the timeline for the project, with likely papers shown as green markers along associated tasks. Many of the diagnostics are either already available (e.g., UTLS jet, tropopause, ASM, and stratospheric polar vortex diagnostics) or are being developed under currently funded projects (e.g., RWB, CAO, and blocking diagnostics; parts of the “regime” analysis) and will thus be available within the first year of this project with little additional support needed. Further, UTLS and general dynamical diagnostics at MLS, SAGE II, SAGE III/ISS, and ACE-FTS measurement locations from MERRA-2 are already publicly available; these diagnostics at MLS locations are also being produced under current funding for JRA-55 and ERA5 and will be available near the beginning of the project [personal communication]. The analysis of the large set of diagnostics being proposed herein is thus feasible because the majority of these products are already available or will be early in this project.

Publications: The expected publications include a paper based primarily on the results of **Objective 1** in year 2, and two papers based primarily on the results of **Objective 3** in year 3.

1.5.2 Management Structure

The PI is responsible for the quality / direction of the proposed research and proper use of awarded funds. The CoIs take direction from the PI and will provide all necessary management data.

As well as oversight of all scientific aspects of the project, the PI has primary responsibility for identifying and characterizing the regions / regimes that will be used for trend analysis and for assessment of the roles of different dynamical processes in these condition spaces.

The CoIs will participate in specific aspects of these studies, including: help develop and produce dynamical diagnostics, participate in and guide studies of composition variability and trends in monsoon regions, participate in analyses assessing the results of regional versus global views of UTLS composition; both CoIs will work with the PI on the trend analysis. The collaborators have advisory roles, including providing guidance on use of the chemical reanalyses and on the dynamical and chemical processes represented therein. They will also provide advice and suggestions on many aspects of the project, including assessment of appropriate regions and coordinates for trend evaluation, impacts of stratosphere-troposphere coupling, and interhemispheric differences relevant to the analyses done for this project.

2 REFERENCES

- [1] S. Tegtmeier, M. I. Hegglin, J. Anderson, A. Bourassa, S. Brohede, D. Degenstein, L. Froidevaux, R. Fuller, B. Funke, J. Gille, A. Jones, Y. Kasai, K. Krüger, E. Kyrölä, G. Lingenfelter, J. Lumpe, B. Nardi, J. Neu, D. Pendlebury, E. Remsberg, A. Rozanov, L. Smith, M. Toohey, J. Urban, T. von Clarmann, K. A. Walker, and R. H. J. Wang. SPARC Data Initiative: A comparison of ozone climatologies from international satellite limb sounders. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 118:12,229–12,247, 2013.
- [2] D. Hubert, J.-C. Lambert, T. Verhoelst, J. Granville, A. Keppens, J.-L. Baray, A. E. Bourassa, U. Cortesi, D. A. Degenstein, L. Froidevaux, S. Godin-Beekmann, K. W. Hoppel, B. J. Johnson, E. Kyrölä, T. Leblanc, G. Lichtenberg, M. Marchand, C. T. McElroy, D. Murtagh, H. Nakane, T. Portafaix, R. Querel, J. M. Russell III, J. Salvador, H. G. J. Smit, K. Stebel, W. Steinbrecht, K. B. Strawbridge, R. Stübi, D. P. J. Swart, G. Taha, D. W. Tarasick, A. M. Thompson, J. Urban, J. A. E. van Gijssel, R. Van Malderen, P. von der Gathen, K. A. Walker, E. Wolfram, and J. M. Zawodny. Ground-based assessment of the bias and long-term stability of 14 limb and occultation ozone profile data records. *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 9:2497–2534, 2016.
- [3] SPARC. *The SPARC Data Initiative: Assessment of stratospheric trace gas and aerosol climatologies from satellite limb sounders*. 2017. SPARC Report No. 8, WCRP-5/2017.
- [4] W. T. Ball, J. Alsing, D. J. Mortlock, J. Staehelin, J. D. Haigh, T. Peter, F. Tummon, R. Stübi, A. Stenke, J. Anderson, A. Bourassa, S. M. Davis, D. Degenstein, S. Frith, L. Froidevaux, C. Roth, V. Sofieva, R. Wang, J. Wild, P. Yu, J. R. Ziemke, and E. V. Rozanov. Evidence for a continuous decline in lower stratospheric ozone offsetting ozone layer recovery. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 18(2):1379–1394, 2018.
- [5] L. F. Millán, N. J. Livesey, M. L. Santee, J. L. Neu, G. L. Manney, and R. A. Fuller. Case studies of the impact of orbital sampling on stratospheric trend detection and derivation of tropical vertical velocities: Solar occultation versus limb emission sounding. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 2016:1–23, 2016.
- [6] L. F. Millán, N. J. Livesey, M. L. Santee, and T. von Clarmann. Characterizing sampling and quality screening biases in infrared and microwave limb sounding. *Atmos. Chem. and Phys.*, 18:4187–4199, mar 2018.
- [7] I. Petropavlovskikh, S. Godin-Beekmann, D. Hubert, R. Damadeo, B. Hassler, and V. Sofieva, editors. *SPARC/IO3C/GAW Report on Long-term Ozone Trends and Uncertainties in the Stratosphere*. 2019. SPARC Report No. 9, GAW Report No. 241, WCRP-17/2018, doi: 10.17874/f899e57a20b.
- [8] G. L. Manney and M. I. Hegglin. Seasonal and regional variations in long-term changes in upper tropospheric jets from reanalyses. *J. Clim.*, 31:423–448, 2018.
- [9] J. R. Albers, J. Perlwitz, A. H. Butler, T. Birner, G. N. Kiladis, Z. D. Lawrence, G. L. Manney, A. O. Langford, and J. Dias. Mechanisms governing interannual variability of stratosphere-to-troposphere ozone transport. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 123(1):234–260, 2018.
- [10] M. L. Breeden, A. H. Butler, J. R. Albers, M. Sprenger, and A. O. Langford. The spring transition of the North Pacific jet and its relation to deep stratosphere-to-troposphere mass transport over western North America. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 21(4):2781–2794, 2021.

-
- [11] M. Toohey, M. I. Hegglin, S. Tegtmeier, J. Anderson, J. A. Añel, A. Bourassa, S. Brohede, D. Degenstein, L. Froidevaux, R. Fuller, B. Funke, J. Gille, A. Jones, Y. Kasai, K. Krüger, E. Kyrölä, J. L. Neu, A. Rozanov, L. Smith, J. Urban, T. von Clarmann, K. A. Walker, and R. H. J. Wang. Characterizing sampling biases in the trace gas climatologies of the SPARC Data Initiative. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 118:11,847–11,862, 2013.
- [12] M. I. Hegglin, S. Tegtmeier, J. Anderson, A. E. Bourassa, S. Brohede, D. Degenstein, L. Froidevaux, B. Funke, J. Gille, Y. Kasai, E. T. Kyrölä, J. Lumpe, D. Murtagh, J. L. Neu, K. Pérot, E. E. Remsberg, A. Rozanov, M. Toohey, J. Urban, T. von Clarmann, K. A. Walker, H.-J. Wang, C. Arosio, R. Damadeo, R. A. Fuller, G. Lingenfelser, C. McLinden, D. Pendlebury, C. Roth, N. J. Ryan, C. Sioris, L. Smith, and K. Weigel. Overview and update of the SPARC Data Initiative: comparison of stratospheric composition measurements from satellite limb sounders. *Earth System Science Data*, 13(5):1855–1903, 2021.
- [13] A. Gettelman, M. I. Hegglin, S.-W. Son, J. Kim, M. Fujiwara, T. Birner, S. Kremser, M. Rex, J. A. Añel, H. Akiyoshi, J. Austin, S. Bekki, P. Braesike, C. Brühl, N. Butchart, M. Chipperfield, M. Dameris, S. Dhomse, H. Garny, S. C. Hardiman, P. Jöckel, D. E. Kinnison, J. F. Lamarque, E. Mancini, M. Marchand, M. Michou, O. Morgenstern, S. Pawson, G. Pitari, D. Plummer, J. A. Pyle, E. Rozanov, J. Scinocca, T. G. Shepherd, K. Shibata, D. Smale, H. Teyssède, and W. Tian. Multimodel assessment of the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere: Tropics and global trends. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 115(D3):n/a–n/a, 2010. D00M08.
- [14] M. I. Hegglin, A. Gettelman, P. Hoor, R. Krichevsky, G. L. Manney, L. L. Pan, S.-W. Son, G. Stiller, S. Tilmes, K. A. Walker, V. Eyring, T. G. Shepherd, D. Waugh, H. Akiyoshi, J. A. Añel, J. Austin, A. Baumgaertner, S. Bekki, P. Braesicke, C. Brühl, N. Butchart, M. Chipperfield, M. Dameris, S. Dhomse, S. Frith, H. Garny, S. C. Hardiman, P. Jöckel, D. E. Kinnison, J. F. Lamarque, E. Mancini, M. Michou, O. Morgenstern, T. Nakamura, D. Olivié, S. Pawson, G. Pitari, D. A. Plummer, J. A. Pyle, E. Rozanov, J. F. Scinocca, K. Shibata, D. Smale, H. Teyssède, W. Tian, and Y. Yamashita. Multimodel assessment of the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere: Extratropics. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 115(D3), 2010.
- [15] J. H. Jiang, H. Su, C. Zhai, V. S. Perun, A. Del Genio, L. S. Nazarenko, L. J. Donner, L. Horowitz, C. Seman, J. Cole, A. Gettelman, M. A. Ringer, L. Rotstayn, S. Jeffrey, T. Wu, F. Brient, J.-L. Dufresne, H. Kawai, T. Koshiro, M. Watanabe, T. S. L’Ecuyer, E. M. Volodin, T. Iversen, H. Drange, M. D. S. Mesquita, W. G. Read, J. W. Waters, B. Tian, J. Teixeira, and G. L. Stephens. Evaluation of cloud and water vapor simulations in CMIP5 climate models using NASA “A-Train” satellite observations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 117(D14), 2012.
- [16] O. Morgenstern, K. A. Stone, R. Schofield, H. Akiyoshi, Y. Yamashita, D. E. Kinnison, R. R. Garcia, K. Sudo, D. A. Plummer, J. Scinocca, L. D. Oman, M. E. Manyin, G. Zeng, E. Rozanov, A. Stenke, L. E. Revell, G. Pitari, E. Mancini, G. Di Genova, D. Visionsi, S. S. Dhomse, and M. P. Chipperfield. Ozone sensitivity to varying greenhouse gases and ozone-depleting substances in CCM1-1 simulations. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 18(2):1091–1114, 2018.
- [17] M. P. Chipperfield, S. Dhomse, R. Hossaini, W. Feng, M. L. Santee, M. Weber, J. P. Burrows, J. D. Wild, D. Loyola, and M. Coldewey-Egbers. On the cause of recent variations in lower
-

- stratospheric ozone. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 45(11):5718–5726, 2018.
- [18] K. Wargan, C. Orbe, S. Pawson, J. R. Ziemke, L. D. Oman, M. A. Olsen, L. Coy, and K. E. Knowland. Recent decline in extratropical lower stratospheric ozone attributed to circulation changes. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 45(10):5166–5176, 2018.
- [19] W. T. Ball, J. Alsing, J. Staehelin, S. M. Davis, L. Froidevaux, and T. Peter. Stratospheric ozone trends for 1985–2018: sensitivity to recent large variability. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, in press, 2019.
- [20] C. Orbe, K. Wargan, S. Pawson, and L. D. Oman. Mechanisms linked to recent ozone decreases in the Northern Hemisphere lower stratosphere. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 125(9):e2019JD031631, 2020. e2019JD031631 10.1029/2019JD031631.
- [21] L. Froidevaux, J. Anderson, H.-J. Wang, R. A. Fuller, M. J. Schwartz, M. L. Santee, N. J. Livesey, H. C. Pumphrey, P. F. Bernath, J. M. Russell III, and M. P. McCormick. Global Ozone Chemistry And Related trace gas Data records for the Stratosphere (GOZCARDS): methodology and sample results with a focus on HCl, H₂O, and O₃. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 15(18):10471–10507, 2015.
- [22] V. F. Sofieva, M. Szeląg, J. Tamminen, E. Kyrölä, D. Degenstein, C. Roth, D. Zawada, A. Rozanov, C. Arosio, J. P. Burrows, M. Weber, A. Laeng, G. P. Stiller, T. von Clarmann, L. Froidevaux, N. Livesey, M. van Roozendaal, and C. Retscher. Measurement report: regional trends of stratospheric ozone evaluated using the Merged GRidded Dataset of Ozone Profiles (MEGRIDOP). *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 21(9):6707–6720, 2021.
- [23] G. Zeng, O. Morgenstern, J. H. T. Williams, F. M. O’Connor, P. T. Griffiths, J. Keeble, M. Deushi, L. W. Horowitz, V. Naik, L. K. Emmons, N. L. Abraham, A. T. Archibald, S. E. Bauer, B. Hassler, M. Michou, M. J. Mills, L. T. Murray, N. Oshima, L. T. Sentman, S. Tilmes, K. Tsigaridis, and P. J. Young. Attribution of stratospheric and tropospheric ozone changes between 1850 and 2014 in CMIP6 models. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 127(16):e2022JD036452, 2022. e2022JD036452 2022JD036452.
- [24] M. Riese, F. Ploeger, A. Rap, B. Vogel, P. Konopka, M. Dameris, and P. Forster. Impact of uncertainties in atmospheric mixing on simulated UTLS composition and related radiative effects. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 117(D16):n/a–n/a, 2012. D16305.
- [25] S. Meul, U. Langematz, P. Kröger, S. Oberländer-Hayn, and P. Jöckel. Future changes in the stratosphere-to-troposphere ozone mass flux and the contribution from climate change and ozone recovery. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 18(10):7721–7738, 2018.
- [26] D. Akritidis, A. Pozzer, and P. Zanis. On the impact of future climate change on tropopause folds and tropospheric ozone. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 19(22):14387–14401, 2019.
- [27] NASA SMD. *Outstanding Questions in Atmospheric Composition, Chemistry, Dynamics and Radiation for the Coming Decade*, 2014. https://espo.nasa.gov/home/content/NASA_SMD_Workshop.
- [28] SPARC. The Stratosphere-troposphere Processes and their Role in Climate (SPARC) implementation plan 2016–2020. Technical report, World Climate Research Program, 2015. http://www.sparc-climate.org/fileadmin/customer/6_Publications/ProgPlan_PDF/SPARC_IP2015_FINAL_redFile.pdf.

-
- [29] J. L. Neu, T. Flury, G. L. Manney, M. L. Santee, N J Livesey, and J Worden. Tropospheric ozone variations governed by changes in the stratospheric circulation. *Nature Geosci.*, 7:340–344, 2014.
- [30] M. I. Hegglin, G. Braathen, T. Leblanc, G. Stiller, J. Tamminen, S. Tegtmeier, C. Voigt, and A. Engel. The GAW/NDACC/SPARC Upper Troposphere and Lower Stratosphere (UTLS) Observation Workshop. *SPARC Newsletter*, 47:39–43, July 2016.
- [31] R. S. Williams, M. I. Hegglin, B. J. Kerridge, P. Jöckel, B. G. Latter, and D. A. Plummer. Characterising the seasonal and geographical variability in tropospheric ozone, stratospheric influence and recent changes. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 19(6):3589–3620, 2019.
- [32] WMO. *Scientific assessment of ozone depletion: 2018*. Global Ozone Res. and Monit. Proj. Rep. 55, Geneva, Switzerland, 2018.
- [33] P. Hoor, D. Kunkel, and W. J. Randel. SPARC workshop “The UTLS: Current status and emerging challenges”. *SPARC Newsletter*, 51:19–23, July 2018.
- [34] K. M. Grise, S. M. Davis, P. W. Staten, and O. Adam. Regional and Seasonal Characteristics of the Recent Expansion of the Tropics. *J. Clim.*, 31(17):6839–6856, 07 2018.
- [35] T. Xian and C. R. Homeyer. Global tropopause altitudes in radiosondes and reanalyses. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 19:5661–5678, 2019.
- [36] C. Lucas and H. Nguyen. Regional characteristics of tropical expansion and the role of climate variability. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 120(14):6809–6824, 2015. 2015JD023130.
- [37] Z. E. Gillett, H. H. Hendon, J. M. Arblaster, and E.-P. Lim. Tropical and extratropical influences on the variability of the southern hemisphere wintertime subtropical jet. *J. Clim.*, 34:4009–4022, 2021.
- [38] G. L. Manney, M. I. Hegglin, and Z. D. Lawrence. Seasonal and regional signatures of ENSO in upper tropospheric jet characteristics from reanalyses. *J. Clim.*, 34(22):9181–9200, 2021.
- [39] N. Butchart and E. E. Remsberg. The area of the stratospheric polar vortex as a diagnostic for tracer transport on an isentropic surface. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 43:1319–1339, 1986.
- [40] P. Hoor, C. Gurk, D. Brunner, M. I. Hegglin, H. Wernli, and H. Fischer. Seasonality and extent of extratropical TST derived from in-situ CO measurements during SPURT. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 4:1427–1442, 2004.
- [41] P. Hoor, H. Wernli, M. I. Hegglin, and H. Bönisch. Transport timescales and tracer properties in the extratropical UTLS. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 10(16):7929–7944, 2010.
- [42] A. Engel et al. Highly resolved observations of trace gases in the lowermost stratosphere and upper troposphere from the SPURT project: an overview. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 6:283–301, 2006.
- [43] M. I. Hegglin, D. Brunner, T. Peter, P. Hoor, H. Fischer, J. Staehelin, M. Krebsbach, C. Schiller, U. Parchatka, and U. Weers. Measurements of NO, NO_y, N₂O, and O₃ during SPURT: implications for transport and chemistry in the lowermost stratosphere. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 6:1331–1350, 2006.
-

-
- [44] G. L. Manney, M. I. Hegglin, W. H. Daffer, M. L. Santee, E. A. Ray, S. Pawson, M. J. Schwartz, C. D. Boone, L. Froidevaux, N. J. Livesey, W. G. Read, and K. A. Walker. Jet characterization in the upper troposphere/lower stratosphere (UTLS): Applications to climatology and transport studies. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 11:6115–6137, 2011.
- [45] L. L. Pan, A. Kunz, C. R. Homeyer, L. A. Munchak, D. E. Kinnison, and S. Tilmes. Commentary on using equivalent latitude in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 12:9187–9199, 2012.
- [46] J. Hu, R. Ren, and H. Xu. Occurrence of winter stratospheric sudden warming events and the seasonal timing of spring stratospheric final warming. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 71:2319–2334, 2014.
- [47] A. H. Butler, A. Charlton-Perez, D. I.V. Domeisen, I. R. Simpson, and J. Sjoberg. Predictability of Northern Hemisphere final stratospheric warmings and their surface impacts. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 46(17-18):10578–10588, 2019.
- [48] T. Wang, Q. Zhang, A. Hannachi, Y. Lin, and T. Hirooka. On the dynamics of the spring seasonal transition in the two hemispheric high-latitude stratosphere. *Tellus A*, 71:1634949, 2019.
- [49] A. H. Butler and D. I. V. Domeisen. The wave geometry of final stratospheric warming events. *Weather and Climate Dynamics*, 2(2):453–474, 2021.
- [50] J. Kidston, A. A. Scaife, S. C. Hardiman, D. M. Mitchell, N. Butchart, M. P. Baldwin, and L. J. Gray. Stratospheric influence on tropospheric jet streams, storm tracks and surface weather. *Nature Geoscience*, 8, 2015.
- [51] D. I. Domeisen and A. H. Butler. Stratospheric drivers of extreme events at the Earth’s surface. *Comm. Earth Environ.*, 1(1):59, December 2020.
- [52] A. H. Butler, J. P. Sjoberg, D. J. Seidel, and K. H. Rosenlof. A sudden stratospheric warming compendium. *Earth System Science Data*, 9(1):63–76, 2017.
- [53] A. D. King, A. H. Butler, M. Jucker, N. O. Earl, and I. Rudeva. Observed relationships between sudden stratospheric warmings and European climate extremes. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 124(24):13943–13961, 2019.
- [54] Z. D. Lawrence, J. Perlwitz, A. H. Butler, G. L. Manney, P. A. Newman, S. H. Lee, and E. R. Nash. The remarkably strong Arctic stratospheric polar vortex of winter 2020: Links to record-breaking Arctic oscillation and ozone loss. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 125(22):e2020JD033271, 2020. e2020JD033271 10.1029/2020JD033271.
- [55] M. P. Baldwin, B. Ayarzagüena, T. Birner, N. Butchart, A. H. Butler, A. J. Charlton-Perez, D. I. V. Domeisen, C. I. Garfinkel, H. Garny, E. P. Gerber, M. I. Hegglin, U. Langematz, and N. M. Pedatella. Sudden stratospheric warmings. *Rev. Geophys.*, 59(1):e2020RG000708, 2021. e2020RG000708 10.1029/2020RG000708.
- [56] J. Huang, P. Hitchcock, A. C. Maycock, C. M. McKenna, and W. Tian. Northern Hemisphere cold air outbreaks are more likely to be severe during weak polar vortex conditions. *Comm. Earth Env.*, 2(1):147, July 2021.
- [57] M. Kretschmer, J. Cohen, V. Matthias, J. Runge, and D. Coumou. The different stratospheric influence on cold-extremes in Eurasia and North America. *npj Clim. Atmos. Sci.*, 1, 2018.
-

-
- [58] J. L. Cohen, L. Agel, M. Barlow, C. I. Garfinkel, and I. White. Linking Arctic variability and change with extreme winter weather in the United States. *Science*, 373(6559):1116–1121, 2021.
- [59] D. W. Waugh, C. I. Garfinkel, and L. M. Polvani. Drivers of the recent tropical expansion in the Southern Hemisphere: Changing SSTs or ozone depletion? *J. Clim.*, 28:6581–6586, 2015.
- [60] A. Solomon and L. M. Polvani. Highly significant responses to anthropogenic forcings of the midlatitude jet in the Southern Hemisphere. *Journal of Climate*, 29(9):3463–3470, 2016.
- [61] S.-W. Son, B.-R. Han, C. I. Garfinkel, S.-Y. Kim, R. Park, N. L. Abraham, H. Akiyoshi, A. T. Archibald, N. Butchart, M. P. Chipperfield, M. Dameris, M. Deushi, S. S. Dhomse, S. C. Hardiman, P. Jöckel, D. Kinnison, M. Michou, O. Morgenstern, F. M. O’Connor, L. D. Oman, D. A. Plummer, A. Pozzer, L. E. Revell, E. Rozanov, A. Stenke, K. Stone, S. Tilmes, Y. Yamashita, and G. Zeng. Tropospheric jet response to Antarctic ozone depletion: An update with chemistry-climate model initiative (CCMI) models. *Env. Res. Lett.*, 13(5):054024, may 2018.
- [62] E.-P. Lim, H. H. Hendon, and D. W. J. Thompson. Seasonal evolution of stratosphere-troposphere coupling in the Southern Hemisphere and implications for the predictability of surface climate. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 123(21):12,002–12,016, 2018.
- [63] E.-P. Lim, H. H. Hendon, G. Boschat, D. Hudson, D. W. J. Thompson, A. J. Dowdy, and J. M. Arblaster. Australian hot and dry extremes induced by weakenings of the stratospheric polar vortex. *Nature Geoscience*, 12(11):896–901, November 2019.
- [64] Z. E. Gillett, J. M. Arblaster, A. J. Dittus, M. Deushi, P. Jöckel, D. E. Kinnison, O. Morgenstern, D. A. Plummer, L. E. Revell, E. Rozanov, R. Schofield, A. Stenke, K. A. Stone, and S. Tilmes. Evaluating the relationship between interannual variations in the Antarctic ozone hole and Southern Hemisphere surface climate in chemistry–climate models. *Journal of Climate*, 32(11):3131–3151, 2019.
- [65] E.-P. Lim, H. H. Hendon, A. H. Butler, D. W. J. Thompson, Z. D. Lawrence, A. A. Scaife, T. G. Shepherd, I. Polichtchouk, H. Nakamura, C. Kobayashi, R. Comer, L. Coy, A. Dowdy, R. D. Garreaud, P. A. Newman, and G. Wang. The 2019 Southern Hemisphere stratospheric polar vortex weakening and its impacts. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 102(6):E1150–E1171, 2021.
- [66] C. S. Y. Huang and N. Nakamura. Local finite-amplitude wave activity as a diagnostic of anomalous weather events. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 73(1):211–229, 2016.
- [67] C. S. Y. Huang and N. Nakamura. Local wave activity budgets of the wintertime Northern Hemisphere: Implication for the Pacific and Atlantic storm tracks. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 44(11):5673–5682, 2017.
- [68] P. Martineau, G. Chen, and D. A. Burrows. Wave events: Climatology, trends, and relationship to Northern Hemisphere winter blocking and weather extremes. *J. Clim.*, 30(15):5675–5697, 2017.
- [69] N. Nakamura and C. S. Y. Huang. Atmospheric blocking as a traffic jam in the jet stream. *Science*, 361(6397):42–47, 2018.
- [70] A. Paradise, C. B. Rocha, P. Barpanda, and N. Nakamura. Blocking statistics in a varying
-

- climate: Lessons from a “traffic jam” model with pseudostochastic forcing. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 76(10):3013–3027, 2019.
- [71] G. Chen, Y. Nie, and Y. Zhang. Jet stream meandering in the Northern Hemisphere winter: An advection–diffusion perspective. *Journal of Climate*, 35(6):2055–2073, 2022.
- [72] E. F. Danielsen. Stratospheric-tropospheric exchange based on radioactivity, ozone and potential vorticity. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 25:502–518, 1968.
- [73] M. A. Shapiro. Turbulent mixing within tropopause folds as a mechanism for the exchange of chemical constituents between the stratosphere and troposphere. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 37:994–1004, 1980.
- [74] M. A. Shapiro, T. Hampel, and A. J. Krueger. The Arctic tropopause fold. *Mon. Weather Rev.*, 115(2):444–454, 1987.
- [75] M. P. Cellitti, J. E. Walsh, R. M. Rauber, and D. H. Portis. Extreme cold air outbreaks over the United States, the polar vortex, and the large-scale circulation. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 111(D2), 2006.
- [76] S. M. Cavallo and G. J. Hakim. Potential vorticity diagnosis of a tropopause polar cyclone. *Monthly Weather Review*, 137(4):1358–1371, 2009.
- [77] L. Papritz, E. Rouges, F. Aemisegger, and H. Wernli. On the thermodynamic preconditioning of Arctic air masses and the role of tropopause polar vortices for cold air outbreaks from Fram Strait. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 124(21):11033–11050, 2019.
- [78] S. P. Lillo, S. M. Cavallo, D. B. Parsons, and C. Riedel. The role of a tropopause polar vortex in the generation of the January 2019 extreme Arctic outbreak. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 78(9):2801–2821, 2021.
- [79] G. L. Manney, A. H. Butler, Z. D. Lawrence, K. Wargan, and M. L. Santee. What’s in a name? on the use and significance of the term “polar vortex”. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 49(10):e2021GL097617, 2022. e2021GL097617 2021GL097617.
- [80] K. A. Biernat, L. F. Bosart, and D. Keyser. A climatological analysis of the linkages between tropopause polar vortices, cold pools, and cold air outbreaks over the central and eastern United States. *Mon. Weather Rev.*, 149(1):189–206, 2021.
- [81] M. Sprenger, H. Wernli, and M. Bourqui. Stratosphere–troposphere exchange and its relation to potential vorticity streamers and cutoffs near the extratropical tropopause. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 64(5):1587–1602, 2007.
- [82] E. A. Barnes, J. Slingo, and T. Woollings. A methodology for the comparison of blocking climatologies across indices, models and climate scenarios. *Clim. Dyn.*, 38(11):2467–2481, Jun 2012.
- [83] T. Woollings, D. Barriopedro, J. Methven, S.-W. Son, O. Martius, B. Harvey, J. Sillmann, A. R. Lupo, and S. Seneviratne. Blocking and its response to climate change. *Current Climate Change Reports*, 4(3):287–300, 2018.
- [84] G. Chen, J. Lu, D. A. Burrows, and L. R. Leung. Local finite-amplitude wave activity as an objective diagnostic of midlatitude extreme weather. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 42(24):10,952–10,960,

- 2015.
- [85] X. Xiong, X. Liu, W. Wu, Q. Yang, and D. K. Zhou. Polar vortex outbreak air transport: Observation using satellite IR sounder derived ozone product and comparison with model. In *AGU Meeting Fall 2021*. AGU, 2021.
- [86] B. Vogel et al. Long-range transport pathways of tropospheric source gases originating in Asia into the northern lower stratosphere during the Asian monsoon season 2012. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 16:15301–15325, 2016.
- [87] M. L. Santee, G. L. Manney, N. J. Livesey, M. J. Schwartz, J. L. Neu, and W. G. Read. A comprehensive overview of the climatological composition of the Asian summer monsoon anticyclone based on 10 years of Aura Microwave Limb Sounder measurements. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 122:5491–5514, 2017.
- [88] X. Yan, P. Konopka, F. Ploeger, A. Podglajen, J. S. Wright, R. Müller, and M. Riese. The efficiency of transport into the stratosphere via the Asian and North American summer monsoon circulations. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 19(24):15629–15649, 2019.
- [89] S. B. Honomichl and L. L. Pan. Transport from the Asian summer monsoon anticyclone over the western Pacific. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 125(13):e2019JD032094, 2020. e2019JD032094 2019JD032094.
- [90] X. Wang, W. Randel, L. Pan, Y. Wu, and P. Zhang. Transient behavior of the Asian summer monsoon anticyclone associated with eastward eddy shedding. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 127(6):e2021JD036090, 2022. e2021JD036090 2021JD036090.
- [91] P. Konopka, J.-U. Grooß, G. Günther, F. Plöger, R. Pommrich, R. Müller, and N. Livesey. Annual cycle of ozone at and above the tropical tropopause: observations versus simulations with the Chemical Lagrangian Model of the Stratosphere (CLaMS). *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 10:121–132, 2010.
- [92] M. Rogal, M. H. Hitchman, M. L. Buker, G. J. Tripoli, I. Stajner, and H. Hayashi. Modeling the effects of Southeast Asian monsoon outflow on subtropical anticyclones and midlatitude ozone over the Southern Indian Ocean. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 115(D20), 2010.
- [93] M. L. Santee, G. L. Manney, L. Froidevaux, N. J. Livesey, W. G. Read, and M. J. Schwartz. Trace gas evolution in the lowermost stratosphere from Aura Microwave Limb Sounder measurements. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 116, 2011.
- [94] F. Ploeger, P. Konopka, R. Müller, S. Fueglistaler, T. Schmidt, J. C. Manners, J.-U. Grooß, G. Günther, P. M. Forster, and M. Riese. Horizontal transport affecting trace gas seasonality in the tropical tropopause layer (TTL). *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 117(D9), 2012.
- [95] S. M. Khaykin, J.-P. Pommereau, E. D. Riviere, G. Held, F. Ploeger, M. Ghysels, N. Amarouche, J.-P. Vernier, F. G. Wienhold, and D. Ionov. Evidence of horizontal and vertical transport of water in the Southern Hemisphere tropical tropopause layer (TTL) from high-resolution balloon observations. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 16(18):12273–12286, 2016.
- [96] C. R. Homeyer and K. P. Bowman. Rossby wave breaking and transport between the tropics

- and extratropics above the subtropical jet. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 70:607–626, 2013.
- [97] J. Ungermann, M. Ern, M. Kaufmann, R. Müller, R. Spang, F. Ploeger, B. Vogel, and M. Riese. Observations of PAN and its confinement in the Asian summer monsoon anticyclone in high spatial resolution. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 16:8389–8403, 2016.
- [98] K.-D. Gottschaldt, H. Schlager, R. Baumann, D. S. Cai, V. Eyring, P. Graf, V. Grewe, P. Jöckel, T. Jurkat-Witschas, C. Voigt, A. Zahn, and H. Ziereis. Dynamics and composition of the Asian summer monsoon anticyclone. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 18(8):5655–5675, 2018.
- [99] L. L. Pan, D. Kinnison, Q. Liang, M. Chin, M. L. Santee, J. Flemming, W. P. Smith, S. B. Honomichl, J. F. Bresch, L. R. Lait, Y. Zhu, S. Tilmes, P. R. Colarco, J. Warner, A. Vuvan, C. Clerbaux, E. L. Atlas, P. A. Newman, T. Thornberry, W. J. Randel, and O. B. Toon. A multi-model investigation of Asian summer monsoon UTLS transport over the Western Pacific. Submitted to *J. Geophys. Res.*, 2022.
- [100] R. Schiemann, D. Lüthi, and C. Schar. Seasonality and interannual variability of the westerly jet in the Tibetan Plateau region. *J. Clim.*, 22:2940–2957, 2009.
- [101] G. L. Manney, M. L. Santee, Z. D. Lawrence, K. Wargan, and M. J. Schwartz. A moments view of climatology and variability of the Asian summer monsoon anticyclone. *J. Clim.*, 34(19):7821–7841, 2021.
- [102] E. J. Highwood and B. J. Hoskins. The tropical tropopause. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, 124:1579–1604, 1998.
- [103] W. Feng, M. P. Chipperfield, S. Davies, G. W. Mann, K. S. Carslaw, S. Dhomse, L. Harvey, C. Randall, and M. L. Santee. Modelling the effect of denitrification on polar ozone depletion for arctic winter 2004/2005. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 11(13):6559–6573, 2011.
- [104] Y. Wu and T. A. Shaw. The impact of the Asian summer monsoon circulation on the tropopause. *Journal of Climate*, 29(24):8689–8701, 2016.
- [105] P. Jing and S. Banerjee. Rossby wave breaking and isentropic stratosphere-troposphere exchange during 1981–2015 in the northern hemisphere. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 123(17):9011–9025, 2018.
- [106] L. L. Pan, W. J. Randel, J. C. Gille, W. D. Hall, B. Nardi, S. Massie, V. Yudin, and R. Khosravi. Tropospheric intrusions associated with the secondary tropopause. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 114, 2009.
- [107] C. Liu and E. A. Barnes. Extreme moisture transport into the Arctic linked to Rossby wave breaking. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 120:3774–3788, 2015. 2014JD022796.
- [108] P. Jing, S. Banerjee, and M. Barrera. Impact of Rossby wave breaking on ozone variation in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere, 1985–2015. *Atmo. Env.*, 222:117122, 2020.
- [109] M. H. Hitchman and A. S. Huesmann. A seasonal climatology of Rossby wave breaking in the 320–2000-K layer. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 64:1922–1940, 2007.
- [110] M. H. Hitchman and A. S. Huesmann. Seasonal influence of the quasi-biennial oscillation on stratospheric jets and Rossby wave breaking. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 66(4):935–946, 2009.
- [111] T. Ndarana and D. W. Waugh. A climatology of Rossby wave breaking on the Southern

- Hemisphere tropopause. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 68:798–811, 2011.
- [112] E. A. Barnes and D. L. Hartmann. Detection of Rossby wave breaking and its response to shifts of the midlatitude jet with climate change. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 117, 2012.
- [113] G. Messori and R. Caballero. On double Rossby wave breaking in the North Atlantic. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 120:11,129–11,150, 2015.
- [114] Anirban Guha, Carlos R. Mechoso, Celal S. Konor, and Ross P. Heikes. Modeling Rossby wave breaking in the southern spring stratosphere. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 73(1):393–406, 2016.
- [115] O. Martius and G. Rivière. Rossby wave breaking: Climatology, interaction with low-frequency climate variability, and links to extreme weather events. in *“Dynamics and Predictability of Large-Scale, High-Impact Weather and Climate Events”*, 2:70–78, 2016.
- [116] C. Michel and G. Rivière. The link between Rossby wave breakings and weather regime transitions. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, 68(8):1730–1748, 2011.
- [117] G. L. Manney and Z. D. Lawrence. The major stratospheric final warming in 2016: dispersal of vortex air and termination of Arctic chemical ozone loss. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 16(23):15371–15396, 2016.
- [118] K. Wargan, B. Weir, G. L. Manney, S. E. Cohn, and N. J. Livesey. The anomalous 2019 Antarctic ozone hole in the GEOS constituent data assimilation system with MLS observations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 125(18):e2020JD033335, 2020. e2020JD033335 2020JD033335.
- [119] G. L. Manney, L. F. Millán, M. L. Santee, K. Wargan, A. Lambert, J. L. Neu, F. Werner, Z. D. Lawrence, M. J. Schwartz, N. J. Livesey, and W. G. Read. Signatures of anomalous transport in the 2019/2020 Arctic stratospheric polar vortex. submitted to *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 2022.
- [120] L. L. Pan, W. J. Randel, B. L. Gary, M. J. Mahoney, and E. J. Hints. Definitions and sharpness of the extratropical tropopause: A trace gas perspective. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 109, 2004.
- [121] P. Hoor, H. Fischer, and J. Lelieveld. Tropical and extratropical tropospheric air in the lowermost stratosphere over Europe: A CO-based budget. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 32:, doi:10.1029/2004GL022018, 2005.
- [122] M. I. Hegglin, C. D. Boone, G. L. Manney, and K. A. Walker. A global view of the extratropical tropopause transition layer (ExTL) from Atmospheric Chemistry Experiment Fourier Transform Spectrometer O₃, H₂O, and CO. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 114, 2009.
- [123] M. A. Olsen, G. L. Manney, and J. Liu. The ENSO and QBO impact on ozone variability and stratosphere-troposphere exchange relative to the subtropical jets. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 124(13):7379–7392, 2019.
- [124] A. Kunz, L. L. Pan, P. Konopka, D. E. Kinnison, and S. Tilmes. Chemical and dynamical discontinuity at the extratropical tropopause based on START08 and WACCM analyses. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 116, 2011.
- [125] J. J. Jin, N. J. Livesey, G. L. Manney, J. H. Jiang, M. J. Schwartz, and W. H. Daffer. Chemical discontinuity at the extratropical tropopause and isentropic stratosphere-troposphere

- exchange pathways diagnosed using Aura MLS data. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 118:3832–3847, 2013.
- [126] G. L. Manney, M. I. Hegglin, W. H. Daffer, M. J. Schwartz, M. L. Santee, and S. Pawson. Climatology of upper tropospheric/lower stratospheric (UTLS) jets and tropopauses in MERRA. *J. Clim.*, 27:3248–3271, 2014.
- [127] S.-Y. Wang, L. Hipps, R. R. Gillies, and J.-H. Yoon. Probable causes of the abnormal ridge accompanying the 2013–2014 California drought: ENSO precursor and anthropogenic warming footprint. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 41:3220–3226, 2014.
- [128] S. H. Lee, J. C. Furtado, and A. J. Charlton-Perez. Wintertime North American weather regimes and the Arctic stratospheric polar vortex. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 46(24):14892–14900, 2019.
- [129] T. Woollings, A. Hannachi, and B. Hoskins. Variability of the North Atlantic eddy-driven jet stream. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, 136:856–868, 2010.
- [130] A. J. Charlton-Perez, L. Ferranti, and R. W. Lee. The influence of the stratospheric state on North Atlantic weather regimes. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 144(713):1140–1151, 2018.
- [131] A. C. Winters. Kinematic processes contributing to the intensification of anomalously strong North Atlantic jets. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 147(737):2506–2532, 2021.
- [132] P. Koch, H. Wernli, and H. C. Davies. An event-based jet-stream climatology and typology. *Int. J. Climatol.*, 26:283–301, 2006.
- [133] A. J. Simmons. Trends in the tropospheric general circulation from 1979 to 2022. *Weather and Climate Dynamics*, 3(3):777–809, 2022.
- [134] A. C. Winters, L. F. Bosart, and D. Keyser. Antecedent North Pacific jet regimes conducive to the development of continental U.S. extreme temperature events during the cool season. *Weather and Forecasting*, 34(2):393–414, 2019.
- [135] Andrew C. Winters. Subseasonal prediction of the state and evolution of the North Pacific jet stream. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 126(17):e2021JD035094, 2021. e2021JD035094 2021JD035094.
- [136] D. W. Waugh and L. M. Polvani. Climatology of intrusions into the tropical upper troposphere. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 27:3857–3860, 2000.
- [137] T. Bayr, D. Dommenges, T. Martin, and S. B. Power. The eastward shift of the Walker Circulation in response to global warming and its relationship to ENSO variability. *Clim. Dyn.*, 43(9-10):2747–2763, 2014.
- [138] C. Spensberger and T. Spengler. Feature-Based Jet Variability in the Upper Troposphere. *J. Clim.*, 33(16):6849–6871, 07 2020.
- [139] G. E. Nedoluha, M. Kiefer, S. Lossow, R. M. Gomez, N. Kämpfer, M. Lainer, P. Forkman, O. M. Christensen, J. J. Oh, P. Hartogh, J. Anderson, K. Bramstedt, B. M. Dinelli, M. Garcia-Comos, M. Hervig, D. Murtagh, P. Raspollini, W. G. Read, K. Rosenlof, G. P. Stiller, and K. A. Walker. The SPARC water vapor assessment II: intercomparison of satellite and ground-

- based microwave measurements. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 17(23):14543–14558, December 2017.
- [140] J. W. Waters, L. Froidevaux, R. S. Harwood, R. F. Jarnot and H. M. Pickett, W. G. Read, P. H. Siegel, R. E. Cofield, M. J. Filipiak, D. A. Flower, J. R. Holden, G. K. Lau, N. J. Livesey, G. L. Manney, H. C. Pumphrey, M. L. Santee, D. L. Wu, D. T. Cuddy, R. R. Lay, M. S. Loo, V. S. Perun, M. J. Schwartz, P. C. Stek, R. P. Thurstans, M. A. Boyles, S. Chandra, M. C. Chavez, G.-S. Chen, B. V. Chudasama, R. Dodge, R. A. Fuller, M. A. Girard, J. H. Jiang, Y. Jiang, B. W. Knosp, R. C. LaBelle, J. C. Lam, K. A. Lee, D. Miller, J. E. Oswald, N. C. Patel, D. M. Pukala, O. Quintero, D. M. Scaff, W. V. Snyder, M. C. Tope, P. A. Wagner, and M. J. Walch. The Earth Observing System Microwave Limb Sounder (EOS MLS) on the Aura satellite. *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, 44:1075–1092, 2006.
- [141] N. J. Livesey, W. G. Read, P. A. Wagner, L. Froidevaux, A. Lambert, G. L. Manney, L. F. Millán Valle, H. C. Pumphrey, M. L. Santee, M. J. Schwartz, S. Wang, R. A. Fuller, R. F. Jarnot, B. W. Knosp, E. Martinez, and R. R. Lay. EOS MLS version 5.0x level 2 and 3 data quality and description document. Technical report, JPL, 2020. Available from <http://mls.jpl.nasa.gov/>.
- [142] N. J. Livesey, J. A. Logan, M. L. Santee, J. W. Waters, R. M. Doherty, W. G. Read, L. Froidevaux, and J. H. Jiang. Interrelated variations of O₃, CO and deep convection in the tropical/subtropical upper troposphere observed by the Aura Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS) during 2004–2011. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 13:579–598, 2013.
- [143] M. A. Olsen, A. R. Douglass, and T. B. Kaplan. Variability of extratropical ozone stratosphere-troposphere exchange using Microwave Limb Sounder observations. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 118:1090–1099, 2013.
- [144] M. J. Schwartz, G. L. Manney, M. I. Hegglin, N. J. Livesey, M. L. Santee, and W. H. Daffer. Climatology and variability of trace gases in extratropical multiple tropopause regions from MLS, HIRDLS and ACE-FTS measurements. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 120:843–867, 2015.
- [145] R. D. Field, G. R. van der Werf, T. Fanin, E. J. Fetzer, R. Fuller, H. Jethva, R. Levy, N. J. Livesey, M. Luo, O. Torres, and H. M. Worden. Indonesian fire activity and smoke pollution in 2015 show persistent nonlinear sensitivity to El Niño-induced drought. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.*, 113:9204–9209, 2016.
- [146] L.F. Millán and G.L. Manney. An assessment of ozone mini-holes representation in reanalyses over the Northern Hemisphere. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 17:9277–9289, 2017.
- [147] C. R. Homeyer, G. L. Manney, L. F. Millán and A. C. Boothe, T. Xian, M. A. Olsen, M. J. Schwartz, Z. D. Lawrence, and K. Wargan. Extratropical upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (ExUTLS). In M. Fujiwara, G. L. Manney, L. J. Grey, and J. S. Wright, editors, *S-RIP Final Report*, chapter 7. 2022.
- [148] R. P. Damadeo, J. M. Zawodny, L. W. Thomason, and N. Iyer. SAGE version 7.0 algorithm: application to SAGE II. *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 6:3539–3561, 2013.
- [149] R. P. Damadeo, J. M. Zawodny, E. E. Remsberg, and K. A. Walker. The impact of nonuniform sampling on stratospheric ozone trends derived from occultation instruments. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 18(2):535–554, 2018.
- [150] M. Cisewski, J. Zawodny, J. Gasbarre, R. Eckman, N. Topiwala, O. Rodriguez-Alvarez,

- D. Cheek, and S. Hall. The Stratospheric Aerosol and Gas Experiment (SAGE III) on the International Space Station (ISS) Mission. In Roland Meynart, Steven P. Neeck, and Haruhisa Shimoda, editors, *Sensors, Systems, and Next-Generation Satellites XVIII*, volume 9241, page 924107. International Society for Optics and Photonics, SPIE, 2014.
- [151] H. J. Ray Wang, Robert Damadeo, David Flittner, Natalya Kramarova, Ghassan Taha, Sean Davis, Anne M. Thompson, Susan Strahan, Yuhang Wang, Lucien Froidevaux, Doug Degenstein, Adam Bourassa, Wolfgang Steinbrecht, Kaley A. Walker, Richard Querel, Thierry Leblanc, Sophie Godin-Beekmann, Dale Hurst, and Emrys Hall. Validation of SAGE III/ISS solar occultation ozone products with correlative satellite and ground-based measurements. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 125(11):e2020JD032430, 2020. e2020JD032430 2020JD032430.
- [152] S. M. Davis, R. Damadeo, D. Flittner, K. H. Rosenlof, M. Park, W. J. Randel, E. G. Hall, D. Huber, D. F. Hurst, A. F. Jordan, S. Kizer, L. F. Millan, H. Selkirk, G. Taha, K. A. Walker, and H. Vömel. Validation of SAGE III/ISS solar water vapor data with correlative satellite and balloon-borne measurements. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 126(2):e2020JD033803, 2021. e2020JD033803 2020JD033803.
- [153] V. F. Sofieva, J. Tamminen, E. Kyrölä, T. Mielonen, P. Veefkind, B. Hassler, and G. E. Bodeker. A novel tropopause-related climatology of ozone profiles. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 14:283–299, 2014.
- [154] M. Park, W. J. Randel, R. P. Damadeo, D. E. Flittner, S. M. Davis, K. H. Rosenlof, N. Livesey, A. Lambert, and W. Read. Near-global variability of stratospheric water vapor observed by SAGE III/ISS. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 126(7):e2020JD034274, 2021. e2020JD034274 2020JD034274.
- [155] K. Bogner, S. Tegtmeier, A. Bourassa, C. Roth, T. Warnock, D. Zawada, and D. Degenstein. Stratospheric ozone trends for 1984–2021 in the SAGE II–OSIRIS–SAGE III/ISS composite dataset. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 22(14):9553–9569, 2022.
- [156] M. I. Hegglin, C. D. Boone, G. L. Manney, T. G. Shepherd, K. A. Walker, P. F. Bernath, W. H. Daffer, P. Hoor, and C. Schiller. Validation of ACE-FTS satellite data in the upper troposphere/lower stratosphere (UTLS) using non-coincident measurements. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 8:1483–1499, 2008.
- [157] J.-H. Koo, K. A. Walker, A. Jones, P. E. Sheese, C. D. Boone, P. F. Bernath, and G. L. Manney. Global climatology based on the ACE-FTS version 3.5 dataset: Addition of mesospheric levels and carbon-containing species in the UTLS. *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transfer*, 186:52–62, 2017.
- [158] P. S. Jeffery, K. A. Walker, C. E. Sioris, C. D. Boone, D. Degenstein, G. L. Manney, C. T. McElroy, L. Millán, D. A. Plummer, N. J. Ryan, P. E. Sheese, and J. Zou. Water vapour and ozone in the upper troposphere – lower stratosphere: Global climatologies from three canadian limb-viewing instruments. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics Discussions*, 2022:1–36, 2022.
- [159] R. Gelaro, W. McCarty, M. J. Suárez, R. Todling, A. Molod, L. Takacs, C. A. Randles, A. Darmenov, M. G. Bosilovich, R. Reichle, K. Wargan, L. Coy, R. Cullather, C. Draper, S. Akella, V. Buchard, A. Conaty, A. M. da Silva, W. Gu, G.-K. Kim, R. Koster, R. Lucchesi, D. Merkova, J. E. Nielsen, G. Partyka, S. Pawson, W. Putman, M. Rienecker, S. D. Schubert, M. Sienkiewicz,

- and B. Zhao. The Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications, Version-2 (MERRA-2). *J. Clim.*, 30:5419–5454, 2017.
- [160] H. Hersbach, B. Bell, P. Berrisford, S. Hirahara, A. Horányi, J. Muñoz-Sabater, J. Nicolas, C. Peubey, R. Radu, D. Schepers, A. Simmons, C. Soci, S. Abdalla, X. Abellan, G. Balsamo, P. Bechtold, G. Biavati, J. Bidlot, M. Bonavita, G. De Chiara, P. Dahlgren, D. Dee, M. Diamantakis, R. Dragani, J. Flemming, R. Forbes, M. Fuentes, A. Geer, L. Haimberger, S. Healy, R. J. Hogan, E. Hólm, M. Janisková, S. Keeley, P. Laloyaux, P. Lopez, C. Lupu, G. Radnoti, P. de Rosnay, I. Rozum, F. Vamborg, S. Villaume, and J.-N. Thépaut. The ERA5 global reanalysis. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, 146(730):1999–2049, 2020.
- [161] S. M. Davis, M. I. Hegglin, R. Dragani, M. Fujiwara, Y. Harada, C. Kobayashi, C. Long, G. L. Manney, E. R. Nash, G. L. Potter, S. Tegtmeier, T. Wang, K. Wargan, and J. S. Wright. Overview of ozone and water vapour. In M. Fujiwara, G. L. Manney, L. J. Grey, and J. S. Wright, editors, *S-RIP Final Report*, chapter 4. 2022.
- [162] J. S. Wright, M. Fujiwara, C. Long, J. Anstey, S. Chabrillat, G. P. Compo, R. Dragani, W. Ebisuzaki, Y. Harada, C. Kobayashi, W. McCarty, A. Molod, K. Onogi, S. Pawson, A. Simmons, D. G. H. Tan, S. Tegtmeier, K. Wargan, J. S. Whitaker, and C.-Z. Zou. Description of reanalysis systems. In M. Fujiwara, G. L. Manney, L. J. Grey, and J. S. Wright, editors, *S-RIP Final Report*, chapter 2. 2022.
- [163] G. L. Manney, M. I. Hegglin, Z. D. Lawrence, K. Wargan, L. F. Millán, M. J. Schwartz, M. L. Santee, A. Lambert, S. Pawson, B. W. Knosp, R. A. Fuller, and W. H. Daffer. Reanalysis comparisons of upper tropospheric/lower stratospheric jets and multiple tropopauses. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, pages 11541–11566, 2017.
- [164] L. Hoffmann and R. Spang. An assessment of tropopause characteristics of the ERA5 and ERA-Interim meteorological reanalyses. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 22(6):4019–4046, 2022.
- [165] S. Tegtmeier, K. Krüger, T. Birner, N. A. Davis, S. Davis, M. Fujiwara, C. R. Homeyer, I. Ivanciu, Y.-H. Kim, B. Legras, G. L. Manney, E. Nishimoto, M. Nützel, R. Pilch Kedzierski, J. S. Wang, T. Wang, and J. S. Wright. Tropical troposphere layer. In M Fujiwara, G L Manney, L J Grey, and J S Wright, editors, *S-RIP Final Report*, chapter 8. 2022.
- [166] Q. Errera, S. Chabrillat, Y. Christophe, J. Deboscher, D. Hubert, W. Lahoz, M. L. Santee, M. Shiotani, S. Skachko, T. von Clarmann, and K. Walker. Technical note: Reanalysis of Aura MLS chemical observations. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 19(21):13647–13679, 2019.
- [167] Global Modeling and Assimilation Office (GMAO). M2-SCREAM inst_3d_asm_met_chm_Nv: 3d, 3-hourly, instantaneous, pressure-level, assimilation, assimilated stratospheric chemistry fields, CoDAS, Icarus-3_2_p9, 0.5x0.625, Greenbelt, MD, USA, Goddard Earth Sciences Data and Information Services Center (GES DISC), accessed: [available by 1 July 2022], 2022.
- [168] K. Wargan, B. Weir, G. L. Manney, S. E. Cohn, K. E. Knowland, P. Wales, and N. J. Livesey. M2-SCREAM: A stratospheric composition reanalysis of Aura MLS data with MERRA-2 transport. submitted to *Earth Systems Science Data*, 2022.
- [169] N. J. Livesey, W. G. Read, P. A. Wagner, L. Froidevaux, A. Lambert, G. L. Manney, L. F. Millán

- Valle, H. C. Pumphrey, M. L. Santee, M. J. Schwartz, S. Wang, R. A. Fuller, R. F. Jarnot, B. W. Knosp, E. Martinez, and R. R. Lay. EOS MLS version 4.2x level 2 data quality and description document. Technical report, JPL, 2018. Available from <http://mls.jpl.nasa.gov/>.
- [170] K Miyazaki, K Bowman, T Sekiya, H Eskes, F Boersma, H Worden, N Livesey, V H Payne, K Sudo, Y Kanaya, M Takigawa, and K Ogochi. Chemical Reanalysis Products, Jet Propulsion Laboratory, accessed: [22 July 2022], 2019.
- [171] K. Miyazaki, H. J. Eskes, and K. Sudo. A tropospheric chemistry reanalysis for the years 2005–2012 based on an assimilation of OMI, MLS, TES, and MOPITT satellite data. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 15(14):8315–8348, 2015.
- [172] K. Miyazaki, H. Eskes, K. Sudo, K. F. Boersma, K. Bowman, and Y. Kanaya. Decadal changes in global surface NO_x emissions from multi-constituent satellite data assimilation. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 17(2):807–837, 2017.
- [173] K. Miyazaki, K. Bowman, T. Sekiya, H. Eskes, F. Boersma, H. Worden, N. Livesey, V. H. Payne, K. Sudo, Y. Kanaya, M. Takigawa, and K. Ogochi. Updated tropospheric chemistry reanalysis and emission estimates, TCR-2, for 2005–2018. *Earth System Science Data*, 12(3):2223–2259, 2020.
- [174] K. Miyazaki and K. Bowman. Evaluation of ACCMIP ozone simulations and ozonesonde sampling biases using a satellite-based multi-constituent chemical reanalysis. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 17(13):8285–8312, 2017.
- [175] W. J. Randel, D. J. Seidel, and L. Pan. Observational characteristics of double tropopauses. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 112, 2007.
- [176] C. Strong and R. E. Davis. Variability in the position and strength of winter jet stream cores related to Northern Hemisphere teleconnections. *J. Clim.*, 21:584–592, 2008.
- [177] C. R. Homeyer, K. P. Bowman, and L. L. Pan. Extratropical tropopause transition layer characteristics from high-resolution sounding data. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 115, 2010.
- [178] S. Limbach, E. Schömer, and H. Wernli. Detection, tracking and event localization of jet stream features in 4-D atmospheric data. *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 5:457–470, 2012.
- [179] D. W. Thompson and J. M. Wallace. Regional climate impacts of the northern hemisphere annular mode. *Science*, 293:85–89, 2001.
- [180] Z. D. Lawrence. Characterization of the stratospheric polar vortex, 2019. PhD Thesis, New Mexico Institute of Mining and Technology.
- [181] D. W. Waugh and W. J. Randel. Climatology of Arctic and Antarctic polar vortices using elliptical diagnostics. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 56:1594–1613, 1999.
- [182] N. J. Matthewman, J. G. Esler, A. J. Charlton-Perez, and L. M. Polvani. A new look at stratospheric sudden warmings. Part III: Polar vortex evolution and vertical structure. *J. Clim.*, 22:1566–1585, 2009.
- [183] Z. D. Lawrence and G. L. Manney. Characterizing stratospheric polar vortex variability with computer vision techniques. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 123(3):1510–1535, 2018. 2017JD027556.

-
- [184] G. L. Manney and L. F. Millán. Derived meteorological products for Aura Microwave Limb Sounder and other satellite datasets, 2007–present. Sign in required.
- [185] G. L. Manney, W. H. Daffer, J. M. Zawodny, P. F. Bernath, K. W. Hoppel, K. A. Walker, B. W. Knosp, C. Boone, E. E. Remsberg, M. L. Santee, V. L. Harvey, S. Pawson, D. R. Jackson, L. Deaver, C. T. McElroy, C. A. McLinden, J. R. Drummond, H. C. Pumphrey, A. Lambert, M. J. Schwartz, L. Froidevaux, S. McLeod, L. L. Takacs, M. J. Suarez, C. R. Trepte, D. C. Cuddy, N. J. Livesey, R. S. Harwood, and J. W. Waters. Solar occultation satellite data and derived meteorological products: Sampling issues and comparisons with Aura Microwave Limb Sounder. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 112(D24S50), 2007.
- [186] A. Jones, K. A. Walker, J. J. Jin, J. R. Taylor, C. D. Boone, P. F. Bernath, S. Brohede, G. L. Manney, S. McLeod, R. Hughes, and W. H. Daffer. Technical note: A trace gas climatology derived from the Atmospheric Chemistry Experiment Fourier Transform Spectrometer (ACE-FTS) data set. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 12(11):5207–5220, 2012.
- [187] X. Zhao, D. Weaver, K. Bognar, G. Manney, L. Millán, X. Yang, E. Eloranta, M. Schneider, and K. Strong. Cyclone-induced surface ozone and HDO depletion in the arctic. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 17(24):14955–14974, 2017.
- [188] G. L. Manney, N. J. Livesey, M. L. Santee, L. Froidevaux, A. Lambert, Z. D. Lawrence, L. F. Millán, J. L. Neu, W. G. Read, M. J. Schwartz, and R. A. Fuller. Record-low Arctic stratospheric ozone in 2020: MLS observations of chemical processes and comparisons with previous extreme winters. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 47(16):e2020GL089063, 2020. e2020GL089063 10.1029/2020GL089063.
- [189] H. E. Attard and A. L. Lang. The impact of tropospheric and stratospheric tropical variability on the location, frequency, and duration of cool-season extratropical synoptic events. *Mon. Weather Rev.*, 147(2):519–542, 2019.
- [190] Hannah E. Attard and Andrea L. Lang. Troposphere–stratosphere coupling following tropospheric blocking and extratropical cyclones. *Mon. Weather Rev.*, 147(5):1781–1804, 2019.
- [191] R. Grotjahn, R. Black, R. Leung, M. F. Wehner, M. Barlow, M. Bosilovich, A. Gershunov, W. J. Gutowski, J. R. Gyakum, R. W. Katz, Y.-Y. Lee, Y.-K. Lim, and Prabhat. North American extreme temperature events and related large scale meteorological patterns: a review of statistical methods, dynamics, modeling, and trends. *Clim. Dyn.*, 46(3):1151–1184, 2016.
- [192] J. Huang and W. Tian. Eurasian cold air outbreaks under different Arctic stratospheric polar vortex strengths. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, 76(5):1245–1264, 2019.
- [193] L. Brunner, G. C. Hegerl, and A. K. Steiner. Connecting atmospheric blocking to European temperature extremes in spring. *J. Clim.*, 30(2):585–594, 2017.
- [194] L. Brunner, N. Schaller, J. Anstey, J. Sillmann, and A. K. Steiner. Dependence of present and future European temperature extremes on the location of atmospheric blocking. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 45(12):6311–6320, 2018.
- [195] N. Szapiro and S. Cavallo. TPVTrack v1.0: a watershed segmentation and overlap correspondence method for tracking tropopause polar vortices. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 11(12):5173–5187, 2018.
-

-
- [196] P.-A. Michelangeli, R. Vautard, and B. Legras. Weather regimes: Recurrence and quasi stationarity. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, 52(8):1237–1256, 1995.
- [197] S. H. Lee, A. J. Charlton-Perez, S. J. Woolnough, and J. C. Furtado. How do stratospheric perturbations influence North American weather regime predictions? *Journal of Climate*, pages 1–56, 2022.
- [198] O. T. Millin, J. C. Furtado, and J. B. Basara. Characteristics, evolution, and formation of cold air outbreaks in the Great Plains of the United States. *Journal of Climate*, 35(14):4585–4602, 2022.
- [199] R. W. Lee, S. J. Woolnough, A. J. Charlton-Perez, and F. Vitart. ENSO modulation of MJO teleconnections to the North Atlantic and Europe. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 46(22):13535–13545, 2019.
- [200] G. Messori, M. Kretschmer, S. H. Lee, and V. Matthias. Stratospheric wave reflection events modulate north american weather regimes and cold spells. *Weather and Climate Dynamics Discussions*, 2022:1–29, 2022.
- [201] B. Pohl and N. Fauchereau. The Southern Annular Mode seen through weather regimes. *Journal of Climate*, 25(9):3336–3354, 2012.
- [202] B. Pohl, T. Saucède, V. Favier, J. Pergaud, D. Verfaillie, J.-P. Féral, Y. Krasniqi, and Y. Richard. Recent climate variability around the Kerguelen Islands (Southern Ocean) seen through weather regimes. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, 60(5):711–731, 2021.
- [203] B. Pohl, V. Favier, J. Wille, D. G. Udy, T. R. Vance, J. Pergaud, N. Dutrievoz, J. Blanchet, C. Kittel, C. Amory, G. Krinner, and F. Codron. Relationship between weather regimes and atmospheric rivers in east Antarctica. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 126(24):e2021JD035294, 2021. e2021JD035294 2021JD035294.
- [204] F. Arizmendi, R. Trinchin, and M. Barreiro. Weather regimes in subtropical south america and their impacts over uruguay. *International Journal of Climatology*, n/a(n/a).
- [205] A. Hochman, G. Messori, J. F. Quinting, J. G. Pinto, and C. M. Grams. Do Atlantic-European weather regimes physically exist? *Geophysical Research Letters*, 48(20):e2021GL095574, 2021. e2021GL095574 2021GL095574.
- [206] C. L. Archer and K. Caldeira. Historical trends in the jet streams. *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 35, 2008.
- [207] C. Peña-Ortiz, D. Gallego, P. Ribera, P. Ordóñez, and M. D. C. Álvarez-Castro. Observed trends in the global jet stream characteristics during the second half of the 20th century. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 118(7):2702–2713, 2013.
- [208] B. Efron and R. J. Tibshirani. *An Introduction to the Bootstrap*, volume 57 of *Monographs on Statistics and Applied Probability*. Chapman and Hall, 1993.
- [209] D. S. Wilks. *Statistical Methods in the Atmospheric Sciences*. Elsevier Academic Press, 3rd edition, 2011. Volume 100, International Geophysics Series.
- [210] E. Maillard Barras, A. Haefele, L. Nguyen, F. Tummon, W. T. Ball, E. V. Rozanov, R. Rüfenacht, K. Hocke, L. Bernet, N. Kämpfer, G. Nedoluha, and I. Boyd. Study of the dependence of
-

- long-term stratospheric ozone trends on local solar time. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 20(14):8453–8471, 2020.
- [211] E. Maillard Barras, A. Haefele, R. Stübi, A. Jouberton, H. Schill, I. Petropavlovskikh, K. Miyagawa, M. Stanek, and L. Froidevaux. DLM estimates of long-term ozone trends from Dobson and Brewer Umkehr profiles. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics Discussions*, 2022:1–24, 2022.
- [212] M. Weber, C. Arosio, M. Coldewey-Egbers, V. E. Fioletov, S. M. Frith, J. D. Wild, K. Tourpali, J. P. Burrows, and D. Loyola. Global total ozone recovery trends attributed to ozone-depleting substance (ODS) changes derived from five merged ozone datasets. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 22(10):6843–6859, 2022.
- [213] J. A. Alsing. dlmmc: dynamical linear model regression for atmospheric time-series analysis. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 4:1157, 2019.
- [214] W. T. Ball, J. Alsing, D. J. Mortlock, E. V. Rozanov, F. Tummon, and J. D. Haigh. Reconciling differences in stratospheric ozone composites. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 17(20):12269–12302, 2017.
- [215] T. G. Shepherd. Bringing physical reasoning into statistical practice in climate-change science. *Climatic Change*, 169(1):2, November 2021.
- [216] D. Kunkel, P. Hoor, I. Petropavlovskikh, and G. L. Manney. Report on the first SPARC OCTAV-UTLS activity, Boulder, CO, USA, 18–20 July 2017. *SPARC Newsletter*, 50:10–13, February 2018.
- [217] T. Leblanc, L. Millán, P. Hoor, and I. Petropavlovskikh. The third SPARC OCTAV-UTLS meeting. *SPARC Newsletter*, 55:13–15, July 2020.
- [218] I. Petropavlovskikh, H. Bönisch, M. Hegglin, P. Hoor, P. Jeffery, D. Kunkel, T. Leblanc, G. Manney, L. Millán, K. Walker, and H. Ye. OCTAV-UTLS activity: update from the March 2022 workshop. *SPARC Newsletter*, 59:23–25, July 2022.
- [219] V. Eyring, S. Bony, G. A. Meehl, C. A. Senior, B. Stevens, R. J. Stouffer, and K. E. Taylor. Overview of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) experimental design and organization. *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 9(5):1937–1958, 2016.
- [220] O. Morgenstern, M. I. Hegglin, E. Rozanov, F. M. O’Connor, N. L. Abraham, H. Akiyoshi, A. T. Archibald, S. Bekki, N. Butchart, M. P. Chipperfield, M. Deushi, S. S. Dhomse, R. R. Garcia, S. C. Hardiman, L. W. Horowitz, P. Jöckel, B. Josse, D. Kinnison, M. Lin, E. Mancini, M. E. Manyin, M. Marchand, V. Marécal, M. Michou, L. D. Oman, G. Pitari, D. A. Plummer, L. E. Revell, D. Saint-Martin, R. Schofield, A. Stenke, K. Stone, K. Sudo, T. Y. Tanaka, S. Tilmes, Y. Yamashita, K. Yoshida, and G. Zeng. Review of the global models used within phase 1 of the Chemistry–Climate Model Initiative (CCMI). *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 10(2):639–671, 2017.
- [221] D. Plummer, T. Nagashima, S. Tilmes, A. Archibald, G. Chiodo, S. Fadnavis, H. Garny, B. Josse, J. Kim, J.-F. Lamarque, O. Morgenstern, L. Murray, C. Orbe, A. Tai, M. Chipperfield, B. Funke, M. Juckes, D. Kinnison, M. Kunze, B. Luo, K. Matthes, P. A. Newman, C. Pascoe, , and T. Peter. CCMI-2022: A new set of Chemistry-Climate Model Initiative(CCMI) community simulations to update the assessment of models and support upcoming ozone assessment activities. *SPARC Newsletter*, 57:22–30, July 2021.